

UNIVERSITÀ DI PISA

SPACECRAFT STRUCTURES AND MECHANISMS COURSE

**ROCKET DESIGN AND STRUCTURAL MODELING & ANALYSIS OF
MICRO-SATELLITE LAUNCH VEHICLE: Inspired by VECTOR-R**

SSM-716

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Master of Science in Aerospace Engineering
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Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1. Report Scope	6
1.2. VECTOR-R Launcher	8
1.3. Micro-satellite Payload	8
1.4. Mission Profile	9
1.5. Materials Selection	10
1.6. Manufacturing Techniques	14
1.7. Reference Frames	15
2. Launcher Design	16
2.1. Mission Analysis	16
2.2. Second-Stage: Preliminary Design	16
2.3. Second-Stage: System Sizing, Design, & Trade-off	19
2.4. First-Stage: Preliminary Design	20
2.5. First-Stage: System Sizing, Design, & Trade-offs	21
2.6. Mass Budget Summary	23
2.7. Components Dimensions Summary	24
2.8. Mass Properties Summary	24
3. Structural Loading	25
3.1. Static Airframe Loads	25
3.2. Dynamic Loads	25
3.3. Loading Cases	26
3.4. Margins of Safety	27
3.5. Launch Simulation & Flight Loads	29
4. Structural Analysis - ANSYS® Workbench	33
4.1. Theoretical Background	33
4.1.1. Analysis Philosophy	33
4.1.2. Analysis Types	33
4.1.3. Large Deflections analysis method	33
4.1.4. Methods of Introducing Loads in FEA	34
4.1.5. Weak Springs analysis method	35
4.2. Static Structural Analysis	35
4.3. Buckling Analysis	36

4.3.1.	Buckling of Isotropic Unstiffened Unpressurized Cylinder in Axial Compression:.....	36
4.3.2.	Buckling of Isotropic Unstiffened Pressurized Cylinders in Axial Compression:.....	36
4.3.3.	Buckling for Orthotropic (Stiffened) Cylinders.....	37
4.4.	Modal Analysis	38
4.5.	ANSYS ACP Composite Analysis System	40
4.6.	ANSYS Analysis Results – Complete Unibody Structure of LOX S1 Tank.....	41
4.6.1.	Static Structural Analysis Results.....	41
4.6.2.	Buckling Analysis Results	54
4.6.3.	Modal Analysis Results.....	56
4.7.	ANSYS Analysis Results – Pressure Vessel.....	64
4.7.1.	Static Structural Analysis Results.....	64
4.7.2.	Buckling Analysis Results	67
4.7.3.	Modal Analysis Results.....	70
4.8.	ANSYS Analysis Results – Outer Body Structure	72
4.8.1.	Static Structural Analysis Results.....	72
4.8.2.	Buckling Analysis Results	74
4.8.3.	Modal Analysis Results.....	76
Conclusion		84
Future Work		84
References.....		85
APPENDIX.....		87
A.	MASS PROPERTIES.....	87
B.	MATLAB® LIVE SCRIPT.....	99
C.	ITERATIVE DESIGN, TRADE-OFFS, & VERIFICATION.....	111
D.	FLIGHT SIMULATOR	121
E.	TECHNICAL DRAWINGS	127

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1 LAUNCH EVENTS.....	9
TABLE 2 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES USED IN ANSYS WORKBENCH SIMULATIONS - ALL HMC HIGH-MODULUS-CARBON MATERIALS.	11
TABLE 3 PROPERTIES OF SELECTED ENGINEERING MATERIALS FORM REFERENCE [4].....	13
TABLE 4 MASS BUDGET: FIRST STAGE - SECOND STAGE	23
TABLE 5 LAUNCHER DIMENSIONS SUMMARY	24
TABLE 6 LAUNCHER MASS PROPERTIES AND CENTER OF MASS	24
TABLE 7 MARGINS OF SAFETY SIGNIFICANCE. [WIJKER 2007]	27
TABLE 8 RECOMMENDED FACTORS OF SAFETY. [SARAFIN 1997]	28

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1 THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPMENT; INSPIRED BY [SARAFIN 1997, LARSON & WERTZ 1992].....	6
FIGURE 2 THE ITERATIVE VERIFICATION OF STRUCTURAL REQUIREMENTS USING VERIFICATION CYCLES. SARAFIN 1997.....	7
FIGURE 3 VECTOR-R AND PAYLOAD CONFIG. COURTESY TO VECTOR-R USER GUIDE	8
FIGURE 4 HIGH PRESSURE COMPOSITE TANKS. IMAGE COURTESY TO MICROCOSM INC. [3]	10
FIGURE 5 THREE MACHINED ALUMINUM ATTACHMENTS TO THE LOWER SKIRT OF FIRST-STAGE.	10
FIGURE 6 LEFT: STAINLESS STEEL CYLINDER CONNECTION SHOWING (LIPS) AND (SLOTS), FIRST-STAGE. RIGHT: CARBON COMPOSITE PLATE AT THE FRONT OF, AND FRAMES LOCATION ON, THE SECOND-STAGE.	12
FIGURE 7 LEFT: SECOND STAGE ALL-COMPOSITE TANK WITH SKIRTS & LONGITUDINAL STRINGERS. RIGHT: CARBON-COMPOSITE FURRING BEAMS.....	12
FIGURE 8 STIFF PLATE STRUCTURE - MANUFACTURING TRACES.	14
FIGURE 9 (LEFT)ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING OF CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITE.	14
FIGURE 10 LAUNCHER MAIN REFERENCE FRAME	15
FIGURE 11 CYLINDRICAL, CM, GLOBAL REFERENCE FRAMES.....	15
FIGURE 12 SPECIFIC IMPULSE TO DENSITY OF LOX & HYDROCARBONS, AT STANDARD TEMPS (LABELED) AND SUBCOOLED.....	17
FIGURE 13 FACTORS OF SAFETY AND LOADS RELATIONSHIP. COURTESY TO WIJKER 2007	28
FIGURE 14 SNAPSHOT FROM 3D FLIGHT SIMULATION OF THE DESIGNED LAUNCHER. END OF RED TRAJECTORY REPRESENTS	29
FIGURE 15 A LOAD FACTOR REPRESENTS INERTIA FORCE AS	34
FIGURE 16 INCREASE IN AXIAL-COMPRESSIVE BUCKLING-STRESS COEFFICIENT OF CYLINDERS DUE TO INTERNAL PRESSURE	37
FIGURE 17 PROJECT SCHEME OF COMPOSITES ANALYSIS USING ACP PREPPOST.....	40
FIGURE 18 COMPLETE UNIBODY STRUCTURE OF S1-LOX TANK – PROJECT SCHEME	41
FIGURE 19 PROJECT TREE FOR THE COMPLETE UNIBODY STRUCTURE OF S1-LOX TANK	42
FIGURE 20 COMPLETE LOADING SETTINGS IN UNIBODY STRUCTURE OF S1-LOX TANK	43
FIGURE 21 COMPONENTS MESHING	43
FIGURE 22 CONNECTION BETWEEN INNERTUBE & STIFFENERS	44
FIGURE 23 DETAILS OF CONTACT REGIONS – CONNECTIONS.....	44
FIGURE 24 CONTACTS BETWEEN PRESSURE VESSEL AND INNERTUBE.....	44
FIGURE 25 TOTAL DEFORMATION OF COMPLETE UNIBODY STRUCTURE OF S1-LOX TANK. IT IS IMPORTANT TO MENTION THAT THE LEAST TRANSLATION ACHIEVED DURING THIS (WEAK SPRING ANALYSIS TYPE WITH FACTOR 6 FOR SPRING STIFFNESS) WAS 1959MM. THE RESULTS SHOW RELATIVE DEFORMATION OF ~0.5MM WHICH IS REALISTIC WHEN COMPARED TO THE RESULTS OF OTHER LOADING CASES WITH (FIXED SUPPORT OR SIMPLY-SUPPORT BOUNDARIES).....	45
FIGURE 26 EQUIVALENT (VON-MISSES) STRESS – COMPLETE UNIBODY STRUCTURE.....	46
FIGURE 27 EQUIVALENT ELASTIC STRAIN – COMPLETE UNIBODY STRUCTURE	47
FIGURE 28 AFT (BACKSIDE) EQUIVALENT STRESS IN THE UNIBODY STRUCTURE CASE, SHOWING CRITICAL VALUES ON THE TANK PART. THE LAST FIGURE SHOWS STRESS IN DIFFERENT LAYERS OF THE PRESSURE VESSEL.	48
FIGURE 29 FRONT SIDE EQUIVALENT STRESS OF UNIBODY STRUCTURE CASE.....	49
FIGURE 30 AFT SIDE EQUIVALENT ELASTIC STRAIN OF THE UNIBODY STRUCTURE CASE	50
FIGURE 31 FRONT SIDE EQUIVALENT ELASTIC STRAIN OF THE UNIBODY STRUCTURE CASE	51

FIGURE 32 STIFFENERS EQUIVALENT STRESS VALUES SHOWN IN THE AFT (TOP) AND FRONT (BOTTOM) SIDES OF THE UNIBODY STRUCTURE CASE.....	52
FIGURE 33 STIFFENERS ELASTIC STRAIN VALUES SHOWN IN THE AFT (TOP) AND FRONT (BOTTOM) SIDES OF THE UNIBODY STRUCTURE CASE.	53
FIGURE 34 FIGURES SHOWING MODES 1 & 2 OF THE BUCKLING. NOTE THE LOAD MULTIPLIER VALUES ARE ALMOST 2 (TWO TIMES APPLIED TEST LOAD IS REQUIRED TO INDUCE LINEAR BUCKLING IN THE STRUCTURE). THIS VALUE WILL DECREASE IN THE CASES OF ONLY OUTER STRUCTURE AND ONLY PRESSURE VESSEL AND WILL BE SHOWN IN FOLLOWING SECTIONS, THIS INDICATE THE STABILIZING EFFECT GAINED FROM THE UNIBODY STRUCTURAL DESIGN). NOTE THAT MODES 3&4 ARE ONLY TRANSLATIONS WITHOUT BUCKLING FAILURE (DUE TO WEAK SPRING ANALYSIS SETTING)	54
FIGURE 35 SECTION VIEW WITH TRUE SCALE (UNAMPLIFIED) DEFORMATION	55
FIGURE 36 FIRST 6 MODAL SHAPES (TRANSLATIONS AND ROTATIONS) SHOW DEFORMATION OF <1MM.....	57
FIGURE 37 PRESSURE VESSEL STATIC ANALYSIS, APPLYING MEOP WITH SAFETY MARGIN =1.5MPA, SHOWING	64
FIGURE 38 EQUIVALENT STRESS IN THE PRESSURE VESSEL UNDER 1.5MPA.	65
FIGURE 39 EQUIVALENT ELASTIC STRAIN OF PRESSURE VESSEL UNDER 1.5MPA.....	66
FIGURE 40 BUCKLING OF PRESSURE VESSEL UNDER 1.5MPA, LOAD MULTIPLIER VALUE OF ~1.3 IS ACHIEVED.....	67
FIGURE 41 BUCKLING MODES 1&2 OF THE OUTER STRUCTURE CARRIED OUT UNDER THE LOADING SCENARIO OF PRE-LIFTOFF WITH FIXED SUPPORT BOUNDARY CONDITION (SEE SECTION 3.3). TESTING LOAD IS 80kN ($J_B=1.33$) SHOWING BUCKLING FAILURE WITH 1MM DEFORMATION AT LOAD MULTIPLIER ~74. IT IS WORTHY TO MENTION THAT THE LAUNCHER WILL BE SUBJECTED TO 60kN BEFORE EXCEEDING LIFT-OFF THRUST TO WEIGHT RATIO.	74
FIGURE 42 BUCKLING MODES 3&4 OF THE OUTER STRUCTURE CARRIED OUT UNDER THE LOADING SCENARIO OF PRE-LIFTOFF WITH FIXED SUPPORT BOUNDARY CONDITION (SEE SECTION 3.3). TESTING LOAD IS 80kN ($J_B=1.33$) SHOWING BUCKLING FAILURE WITH 1MM DEFORMATION AT LOAD MULTIPLIER ~77.IT IS WORTHY TO MENTION THAT THE LAUNCHER WILL BE SUBJECTED TO 60kN BEFORE EXCEEDING LIFT-OFF THRUST TO WEIGHT RATIO.	75
FIGURE 43 ACP-PRE MODEL-TREE.....	81
FIGURE 44 FABRIC PROPERTIES (TOP) - STACKUP PROPERTIES (BOTTOM)	82
FIGURE 45 PLYS ORIENTATION - WOVEN CASE AND UNIDIRECTIONAL CASE.	83

ABSTRACT

Microsatellite launch vehicles are currently being developed in a rapid manner to fulfill needs of Micro- and Nano- satellites market, mainly for scientific and research uses. Light-weight structures and composite materials are key aspects in developing this kind of launchers. This technical report will be investigating development processes of a Microsatellite Launcher from the perspective of Space Structures, focusing on preliminary design, modeling, and structural analysis & simulation, and design verification. In order to define design requirements effectively, Rocket Design study was performed for a launcher inspired by Vector-R Microsatellite Launch Vehicle. Flight simulations were carried out to validate the rocket design study outputs, as well as to provide flight dynamics data to assess critical loading conditions throughout the mission. Structural analysis was carried out on "First-Stage Unibody-Structure of LOX Tank" using ANSYS workbench (Static Structural, Linear-Buckling, & Modal Analyses). The structural analysis of this part is crucial since it is the largest in terms of mass and size. Verification and refining of design of this part is crucial for the whole launcher development process.

1. Introduction

1.1. Report Scope

This report aims to study and perform different structural analysis processes to investigate and verify a preliminary design of a space structure. The process of development of any space structure starts by describing generally what the structure is intended to do, followed by intensive definition of the structure's key requirements as well as structural elements and components specified requirements [Sarafin 1997].

The space structure under investigation is a Micro-satellite Launch Vehicle, capable of launching small payloads to low earth orbit. The launcher is inspired by Vector-R launcher of the American startup Vector Space Systems. This vehicle is made of composite structures mainly and utilizes unibody propellant tank structures, which means the unibody structure include both the pressure vessel and the outer structure carrying the main loads of the whole launch vehicle. Metallic parts are used to connect different unibody structures of propellant tanks together and is investigated briefly in following sections of chapter 1. Composite structures are dealt with intensively in all chapters of this report.

The process of development of the Micro-satellite Launch Vehicle typically starts by defining mission requirements which all the systems will be built on. Consequently, Preliminary Design development takes based on the requirements, and further *Iterative Verification* (Fig.2) is carried-on to refine the design.

Figure 1 The Process of Development; inspired by [Sarafin 1997, Larson & Wertz 1992]

tural Requirements using Verification Cycles. Saraf

1.2. VECTOR-R Launcher

Vector-R is a small satellite launcher developed by Vector Space Systems that was selected for Small Business Innovation Research (SBIR) from NASA in 2015 for the Upper-Stage development. Later in 2016 the company was awarded another SBIR fund from the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA). First commercial launches are planned in 2020.

Vector-R utilizes a Pressure-Fed pressurization system. Not like the convention Pressure-Fed system, that uses external pressurant like Helium stored in heavy titanium high pressure tanks, Vector-R is “Autogenously-Pressurized”, which means propellant itself is used to pressurize the propellant tanks without the need of external pressurant.

“In the proposed concept, electrically-driven micropumps drive a small portion of each propellant over a heat exchanger at the engine to pressurize the tanks. Excess flow can be diverted to the engine as needed,” the proposal states.

The above-mentioned pressurization technique is the main reason behind having a lightweight small vehicle – along with the carbon composite airframe- like Vector-R, being capable of carrying a 60kg payload to LEO.

“This approach reduces system mass, complexity and acquisition cost as well as operational costs,” the proposal adds. “It eliminates the need for all high-pressure tanks and associated components.”

Vector-R is running of LOX/Liquid Propylene (subcooled) that have superior performance to RP-1 [1] and offers very close performance to methane [2]. Liquid Propylene possess higher densities when subcooled relatively close to that of LOX.

1.3. Micro-satellite Payload

As per the User guide the Launch Vehicle will possess payload capabilities as follows;

- ✓ 60 kg to 250 km circular @ 38 degrees inclination low Earth orbit (LEO) from MARS (Wallops) – *[The design and calculations carried in this report are based on this input]*
- ✓ 32 kg to 500 km Sun Synchronous Orbit (SSO) from PSCA (Kodiak) or SLC-8 (Vandenberg)
- ✓ 60 kg available to lower inclinations / equatorial sites (future capability)
- ✓ Payloads can launch without fully enclosed deployers
- ✓ Suitable for payloads with onboard propulsion systems

Figure 3 Vector-R and Payload Config. Courtesy to Vector-R User Guide

1.4. Mission Profile

Main events for the Vector-R Launcher are illustrated below. These data are used in the *Mission Analysis* part for the *Launcher Design*, and in the prediction of the *Flight Loads* within the *Flight Dynamics Model*.

It has to be noticed that accurate values for flight loads are not known, since this vehicle is new and still under development launcher. Using mission profile information can only help with rough figures to predict flight loads. Informatin for Second Stage Engine Cut-off relies on the final orbit and type of maneuver.

TIME	EVENT
T +0s	Lift-Off
T +4.7s	Launch
T +216s	MECO (108km alt. – 87km d.r.)
T +225s	Separation & Second-Stage Ignition
T +251	Fairing Separation
T +427s	SECO (depending on final orbit)
T +546s	Microsatellites separation
T +1369	Fuel Depletion

Table 1 Launch Events

1.5. Materials Selection

Main structure of the Launch Vehicle is a **Carbon-composite pressurized light-weight structure**. The Tanks are believed to be supplied by *Microcosm Inc.* and the *Scorpius® Space Launch Company* and employ High Pressure Composite Tanks Technology. All-composite LOX tanks have been produced using similar processes as the fuel tanks, and they are cryogenically compatible [3]. Comments on manufacturing are provided in this report under *Section 1.6 Manufacturing Techniques*. Figure 4 shows the tanks of the First-Stage of the Launcher with upper and lower Stainless-steel skirts. In Figure 5, three aluminum attachments to the lowers part of the First-Stage, act as structural support on the Launch Pad.

Figure 4 High Pressure Composite Tanks. Image courtesy to Microcosm Inc. [3]

The *composite Over-wrapped* propellant tanks employ **Carbon Fiber- Reinforce Epoxy Composite** with $\pm 45^\circ$ fibers orientation, for the tank main structure, to overcome wide range of Axial, Bending, and Shear loads. While the Over-wrap, of the external tank structure, most probably is made of **Kevlar Fiber-Reinforced Epoxy composite** due to its mechanical properties that are shown in the table 3. Mechanically, **Aramid Fibers** have longitudinal tensile strength and tensile moduli that are higher than those of higher polymeric fiber materials. In addition, Aramids are known for toughness, impact resistance, resistance to creep and fatigue failure [4]. It is also important to notice the end parts (*skirts*) that are made of **Stainless Steel**, would be necessary as transition and interconnecting element between other tanks or parts of the launcher.

Figure 5 Three machined Aluminum attachments to the Lower Skirt of First-Stage.

As for the tanks of the Second-Stage, Figure 7-Left: shows a *Uni-body, all-composite Tank* with skirts and circumferential and longitudinal stringers. Figure 7-Right: shows longitudinal stringers, *Carbon-composite Furring Beams* on the internal side of the Second-Stage skin. Additive manufacturing techniques are employed for these integrated features, according to reference paper [5]. Details about Stringers integration to the tank structure, as well as plies orientation of the composite material are explained in the patent number US008449705B1 (year 2013) [6].

Material Properties and Design Philosophy

The *Unibody structure* of the launcher propellant tanks, consist of composite *pressure vessel* and *outer structure* (load carrying structure). The *outer structure* is made of two parts; Firstly, a *monocoque cylinder* made of quasi-isotropic structure of woven carbon-composite oriented plies, that carries axial, bending, and torsional loads to an extent. Secondly, a *stiffened-skin cylinder* consisting of carbon composite light-weight *stiffeners* and wrapped by composite thin *outer-skin*. *Stiffeners* are axial members intended to increase the buckling stress of the skin (as opposed to stringers, which carry most of the axial load), while *outer-skin* is typically responsible to transfer shear and torsion by diagonal tension [Sarafin 1997]. The pressure vessel contributes to stabilizing the outer structure and react to the radial component of diagonal tension loads. Two types of composites are employed in the structure; *Unidirectional High-modulus Carbon Epoxy* composite used for the Longitudinal Elements (Stiffeners), and *Woven High-modulus Carbon Epoxy* composite used for the Pressure Vessel as well as cylindrical parts of the outer structure.

As for the *Plies Orientation Angles* and *Fabrics Alignment*, detailed discussion and illustrative figures are included in the end of chapter 4.

	Unidirectional Carbon Epoxy Composite (395GPa)	Woven Carbon Epoxy Composite (395GPa)
Density in kg/m³	1540	1480
Young's Modulus – x MPa	20900	91820
Young's Modulus – y MPa	9450	91820
Young's Modulus – z MPa	9450	9000
Poisson's Ration – x	0.27	0.05
Poisson's Ration – y	0.4	0.3
Poisson's Ration – z	0.27	0.3
Shear Modulus – x MPa	5500	19500
Shear Modulus – y MPa	3900	3000
Shear Modulus – z MPa	5500	3000
Tensile Strength – x MPa	1979	829
Tensile Strength – y MPa	26	829
Tensile Strength – z MPa	26	50
Shear Strength – x MPa	100	120
Shear Strength – y MPa	50	50
Shear Strength – z MPa	50	50

Table 2 Mechanical Properties of Composites used in ANSYS Workbench simulations - all HMC High-Modulus-Carbon materials.

Figure 6 Left: Stainless Steel cylinder connection showing (Lips) and (Slots), First-Stage. Right: Carbon composite Plate at the front of, and Frames location on, the Second-Stage.
Image courtesy to Vector Space Systems.

Figure 7 Left: Second Stage All-Composite Tank with Skirts & Longitudinal Stringers. Right: Carbon-Composite Furring Beams
Image courtesy to Microcosm

Characteristics of Several Fiber-Reinforcement Materials

<i>Material</i>	<i>Specific Gravity</i>	<i>Tensile Strength [GPa (10⁶ psi)]</i>	<i>Specific Strength (GPa)</i>	<i>Modulus of Elasticity [GPa (10⁶ psi)]</i>	<i>Specific Modulus (GPa)</i>
Whiskers					
Graphite	2.2	20 (3)	9.1	700 (100)	318
Silicon nitride	3.2	5–7 (0.75–1.0)	1.56–2.2	350–380 (50–55)	109–118
Aluminum oxide	4.0	10–20 (1–3)	2.5–5.0	700–1500 (100–220)	175–375
Silicon carbide	3.2	20 (3)	6.25	480 (70)	150
Fibers					
Aluminum oxide	3.95	1.38 (0.2)	0.35	379 (55)	96
Aramid (Kevlar 49)	1.44	3.6–4.1 (0.525–0.600)	2.5–2.85	131 (19)	91
Carbon ^a	1.78–2.15	1.5–4.8 (0.22–0.70)	0.70–2.70	228–724 (32–100)	106–407
E-glass	2.58	3.45 (0.5)	1.34	72.5 (10.5)	28.1
Boron	2.57	3.6 (0.52)	1.40	400 (60)	156
Silicon carbide	3.0	3.9 (0.57)	1.30	400 (60)	133
UHMWPE (Spectra 900)	0.97	2.6 (0.38)	2.68	117 (17)	121
Metallic Wires					
High-strength steel	7.9	2.39 (0.35)	0.30	210 (30)	26.6
Molybdenum	10.2	2.2 (0.32)	0.22	324 (47)	31.8
Tungsten	19.3	2.89 (0.42)	0.15	407 (59)	21.1

^aAs explained in Section 13.8, because these fibers are composed of both graphitic and turbostratic forms of carbon, the term *carbon* instead of *graphite* is used to denote these fibers.

Table 3 Properties of Selected Engineering Materials from Reference [4]

1.6. Manufacturing Techniques

Additive Manufacturing is employed extensively in modern composite manufacturing. As shown in the previous section, the longitudinal-Stringers and Circumferential-Stringers embedded in the tanks' structures are manufactured using this technique. Technique used particularly, is believed to be *Material Extrusion (3D-Printing)* due to its cost-effectiveness. In which the material is deposited in either filament or in paste form in the material extrusion process. The process through which the filament is melted and extruded is known as *fused filament fabrication* while it is known as *liquid deposition modeling* if paste is utilized [7].

Figure 8 Stiff Plate Structure - Manufacturing traces.

As for the airframe longitudinal elements (furring beams and flat strip stiffeners) classic processing techniques are believed to be mainly used; such as [8]:

- Pultrusion
- Resin Transfer Molding (RTM)
- Structural Reaction Injection Molding (SRIM)
- Sheet Molding Compound (SMC).

Cylindrical Tanks, with spherical or semispherical ends, are fabricated by **Filament Winding Process**. Filament winding is a process where resin and fibers are combined at the time of curing. This process is widely used in composite tank manufacturing due to its low cost and rapid processing time. The filaments being towed around the mandrel – the applied tows – can be combined with a resin matrix immediately prior to application to the mandrel (*Wet Winding*) or the tows can be a (*Towpreg*) which is a fiber/resin combination ready made by a vendor. *Towpreg* winding is used to make parts that require a narrow resin content range. The resin/fiber tows are generally processed at higher speeds compared to *wet winding*.

The *Stiff Plates* incorporated in the structure, as shown in (Figure 6 – Right & Figure 8), it can be noticed that a *layer-by-layer effect* is present for the *deposited paste material*. With a typical shape of extrusion nozzle. The deposit material is aligned in vertical direction. This also implies the use of *Material Extrusion (3D-Printing)* additive manufacturing technique for *Plate* parts, so as the *Frames* in the airframe structure.

Figure 9 (left) Additive Manufacturing of Continuous Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composite. [Image Courtesy to Koumoulos et al. Journal of Composite Science 2019]. (Right) Towpreg Tank winding.

1.7. Reference Frames

Through out the study two types of reference frames are used; *Cartesian Reference frame* (x,y,z) usually denoted as main Global Reference Frame, with its origin at the base of the Launcher, as shown in the figure 10. In case of treating separate parts, the cartesian reference frame is centered at the center of mass of this body part.

The second type is *Cylindrical Reference Frame*, with z-axis considered as the principal axis, x-axis is the radial axis, and y-axis denotes the circumferential direction, figure 11.

Figure 11 Cylindrical, CM, Global Reference Frames

Figure 10 Launcher Main Reference Frame

2. Launcher Design

2.1. Mission Analysis

The required *final orbit* for the launcher’s Micro-satellites payload is 250km circular orbit with 38° inclination. The launching site suggested is MARS-Wallops (37.940194°N). Thus, the final velocity to be considered;

$$V_{final} \cong 7755 \text{ m/s}$$

The First-Stage of the Launcher must have,

$$\Delta V_{s1} = 6700 \text{ m/s}$$

to be able to overcome drag losses, and losses due to gravity.

$$V_D \cong 100 \text{ m/s}$$

Taking in to account the velocity of the launch site,

$$V_{L^o} = 464.5 \cos(38^\circ) = 366 \text{ m/s}$$

the final velocity at MECO, after 150s of lift-off, achieved is;

$$V_{MECO} = 6700 - 9.81 * 150 - 100 + 366 \cong 5495 \text{ m/s}.$$

Thus, Second-Stage is supposed to cover $\Delta V_{s2} \cong 2800 \text{ m/s}$, taking into account deorbiting and a design margin.

Finally, the total velocity budget $\Delta V_{total} = 9500 \text{ m/s}$.

2.2. Second-Stage: Preliminary Design

Requirements	Quantity	Comments
ΔV	2800 (m/s)	Required for 250 circular orbit altitude raising to 108km at t=150s, MECO insertion point
$m_{payload}$	90 (kg)	Including 60kg micro-sats and rest design margin
Propellant	Liquid Propylene/LOX	Properties mentioned in following section
Engine Thrust	~4,000N	LP-2 Space Engine
Inert-mass-fraction	0.25	f_{inert}

2.2.1. Mass & Envelope Estimation for [Space-Engine]

Engine Thrust:Weight	$\frac{F}{W}$	= 30 (conservative value according to [1])
Engine Mass	$m_E = \frac{F}{g_0 \frac{F}{W}}$	= 13.6kg
Engine Length	$L_E = 0.0054 F + 31.92$	= 53.5cm Reference [9] Section 5.3.1
Engine Diameter	$D_E = 0.00357 F + 14.48$	= 28.8cm

2.2.2. Propellant Properties

According to data analyzed from reference [10], assumptions including a chamber pressure of 20 MPa and an expansion ratio of 40. Specific impulses are calculated with *Rocket Propulsion Analysis Software*. The grey contour lines show figures of merit for an SSTO with an ideal delta-V of 10 km/s, according to a particular mass model. Each curve covers the range from peak specific impulse to peak impulse density. Figure 12 shows LOX with hydrocarbons. Each fuel is plotted twice, once for propellants at standard temperatures and once chilled. Only the standard-temperature curves are labeled.

Figure 12 Specific Impulse to Density of LOX & Hydrocarbons, at Standard Temps (labeled) and Subcooled. Courtesy of [Proponent](#) @nasaspaceflight.com

Accordingly, specific impulse and fuel density for Second-Stage Engine are assumed to be;

PROPELLANT	Density ρ (kg/m³)	O/F	Specific Impulse $I_{sp\ vac.}$ (s)
Liquid Propylene	1060 (chilled)	2.6	350
Liquid Oxygen	1140		

2.2.3. Pressurizing System

Pressure-fed systems classically use external pressurant tanks, most often of Helium or Nitrogen. A main withdraw of this conventional way is the high structural mass of the pressurant tank. Modern lightweight Launchers utilize different techniques to get rid of this excess mass. A family of Launchers by Microcosm Inc. use a patented technique called *Tridyne-Pressurization* [11], where inert Helium or nitrogen gasses are used enriched with small percentage of Hydrogen and Oxygen gasses that react in a

catalyst to heat up the pressurant gas inside the tanks to avoid expansion cooling and the loss of specific volume which leads to the need of more gas. This technique leads to dramatic decrease in amount of pressurant gas needed and thus the structural mass associated with pressurant tankage.

As for Vector-R “Autogenous-Pressurization System” is used, which means propellant itself is used to pressurize the propellant tanks without the need of external pressurant gas. It is proposed that, electrically-driven micropumps are used to drive a small portion of each propellant over a heat exchanger at the engine to pressurize the tanks.

For simplifying the preliminary design, the Autogenous-Pressurization system will be assumed for the First and Second Stages of the Launcher.

2.2.4. Cooling System

LP-1 and LP-2 engines employ two cooling techniques;

- Ablative Cooling System
- Film Cooling.

In Ablative Cooling, during the combustion hot gases vaporize the ablator material that lines the combustion chamber wall. These materials tend to be silica, quartz, carbon cloth and resin composites attached to the thrust chamber, as already seen on the engines used in Vector-R. As for Film Cooling (Boundary Layer Cooling), the injectors intentionally throw liquid fuel in vicinity of the chamber walls. A film of liquid propellant is formed along the chamber walls; as the cooler film flows along the walls it increases the thermal resistance and reduces the wall temperature.

2.2.5. Propellant Mass Estimation

$$m_{propellant} = \frac{m_{payload} [e^{\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}} - 1] (1 - f_{inert})}{1 - f_{inert} \cdot e^{\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}} = 195.59kg$$

$$m_{fuel} = \frac{m_{propellant}}{1 + O/F} = 54.5kg$$

$$m_{oxidizer} = m_{propellant} \frac{O/F}{1 + O/F} = 141.5kg$$

$$V_{fuel} = \frac{m_{fuel}}{\rho_{fuel}} \cong 0.055m^3$$

$$V_{oxidizer} = \frac{m_{ox}}{\rho_{ox}} \cong 0.130m^3$$

2.3. Second-Stage: System Sizing, Design, & Trade-off

2.3.1. Propellant Tanks Pressurizing for (PRESSURE-FED SYSTEMS)

$$P_{tank} = (10^{-0.1281[\log(V_{tank}) + 0.2498]}) \times 10^6$$

$$P_{tank\ Fuel} = 1.356\ MPa$$

$$P_{tank\ OX} = 1.214\ MPa$$

$$p_b = fs \cdot MEOP \text{ (Burst Pressure)}$$

$$p_{b\ Fuel} = 2.712\ MPa$$

$$p_{b\ OX} = 2.428\ MPa$$

2.3.2. Propellant Tank Sizing

Propellant Tanks Material	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Ultimate Tensile Strength F_{tu} (GPa)	Structure Efficiency Factor $F_{tu} / \rho \cdot g_0$ (km)	Tank Mass Factor ϕ_{tank} (m)
Graphite Fibers Composite	1550	0.862	58.88	10,000

Data from SPAD Book [9]

For preliminary design, either cylindrical tanks with spherical ends or perfect spherical shape tanks shall be considered.

<u>Fuel Tank (cylindrical)</u>	<u>Oxidizer Tank (cylindrical)</u>
$V_{Fuel\ Tank} = 0.055m^3$	$V_{OX\ Tank} = 0.130m^3$
$r_s = 0.20m$ $l_c = \frac{V_{fuel\ Tank} - \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} \cong 0.20m$	$r_s = r_c = 0.20m$ $l_c = \frac{V_{OX\ Tank} - \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} = 0.80m$
Include 10cm for titanium caps	
$OAL = 0.70m$ $\phi_{fuel\ tank} = 0.40m$	$OAL = 1.30m$ $\phi_{fuel\ tank} = 0.40m$

Tank Masses are estimated using pV/W approach [9]

$$\phi_{tank} = \frac{p_b \cdot V}{m_{tank} \cdot g_0}$$

$$m_{tank\ Fuel} \cong 2.0kg * 2_{external\ structure} = 4.0kg$$

$$m_{tank\ Ox} \cong 3.5kg * 2_{external\ structure} = 7.0kg$$

2.3.3. Pressurant System

Considering the “Autogenous-Pressurization System” discussed previously. No external pressurant tankage will be required. However, we can assume using six (Electrically-driven Micro-pumps) capable of pumping both liquid and gas, along with electric power source to have;

$$mass_{micro-pumps} = 6 \times 170gm = 1.20kg$$

$$mass_{power\ unit} = 3.0kg$$

2.3.4. Masses of Thrust Vector Control (TVC) and Feed-System

As proposed by SPAD Book [9], this mass is included in the total Engine mass preliminary estimate.

2.3.5. Structural Mounts Masses

Represents about 5-10% from main components masses. Calculated through;

$$0.1(m_E + m_{Propellant\ Tanks}) \approx 3kg$$

2.4. First-Stage: Preliminary Design

Requirements	Quantity	Comments
ΔV	6700 (m/s)	Required for 108km MECO insertion point at t=150s
$m_{payload}$	350 (kg)	Including total mass of Second-Stage with payload and design margin.
Propellant	Liquid Propylene/LOX	—
Engine Thrust	~85,000N	(x3) LP-1 Sea Level Engine
Inert-mass-fraction	0.09	f_{inert}

2.4.1. Mass & Envelope Estimation for (First-Stage Engine)

Engine Thrust:Weight	$\frac{F}{W}$	= 70 Figure according to [1]
Engine Mass (three LP-1 Engines are used)	$m_E = \frac{F}{g_0 \frac{F}{W}}$	= 41.26kg (per Engine)
Engine Length	$L_E = 0.000\ 03042\ F + 327.7$	= 328.5mm Reference [9] Section 5.3.1
Engine Diameter	$D_E = 0.000\ 02359\ F + 181.3$	= 181.9mm

2.4.2. Propellant Properties

PROPELLANT	Density ρ (kg/m³)	O/F	Specific Impulse I_{sp} sea level (s)
Liquid Propylene	1060 (chilled)	2.6	346
Liquid Oxygen	1140		

2.4.3. Pressurizing System

Pressure-Fed “Autogenous-Pressurization” system is used, where the propellant is heated through a heat exchanger at the engine and then returned to the propellant tanks to increase tank pressure.

2.4.4. Cooling System

Ablative cooling system is used for the LP-1 engine along with film (boundary) layer cooling, where propellant is injected near the combustion chamber walls to reduce their temperature.

2.4.5. Propellant Mass Estimation

$$m_{propellant} = \frac{m_{payload} [e^{\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}} - 1] (1 - f_{inert})}{1 - f_{inert} \cdot e^{\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}} = 5607.2$$

$$m_{fuel} = \frac{m_{propellant}}{1 + \frac{O}{F}} = 1557.6 \text{ kg}$$

$$m_{oxidizer} = m_{propellant} \frac{O/F}{1 + O/F} = 4049.6 \text{ kg}$$

$$V_{fuel} = \frac{m_{fuel}}{\rho_{fuel}} \cong 1.5 \text{ m}^3$$

$$V_{oxidizer} = \frac{m_{ox}}{\rho_{ox}} \cong 3.6 \text{ m}^3$$

2.5. First-Stage: System Sizing, Design, & Trade-offs

2.5.1. Propellant Tanks Pressurizing for (PRESSURE-FED SYSTEMS)

$$P_{tank} = (10^{-0.1281[\log(V_{tank}) + 0.2498]}) \times 10^6$$

$$P_{tank \text{ Fuel}} = 0.882 \text{ MPa}$$

$$P_{tank \text{ OX}} = 0.788 \text{ MPa}$$

$$p_b = fs \cdot \text{MEOP (Burst Pressure)}$$

$$p_b \text{ Fuel} = 1.764 \text{ MPa}$$

$$p_b \text{ OX} = 1.576 \text{ MPa}$$

2.5.2. Propellant Tanks Sizing

Propellant Tanks Material	Density ρ (kg/m³)	Ultimate Tensile Strength F_{tu} (GPa)	Structure Efficiency Factor $F_{tu} / \rho \cdot g_0$ (km)	Tank Mass Factor ϕ_{tank} (m)
Graphite Fibers Composite	1550	0.862	58.88	10,000

For preliminary design of propellant tanks in Stage-1, cylindrical tanks with spherical ends shall be considered.

Fuel Tank	Oxidizer Tank
$V_{Fuel\ Tank} = 1.5m^3$	$V_{OX\ Tank} = 3.6m^3$
$r_s = r_c = 0.481m$	
$l_c = \frac{V_{Fuel\ Tank} - \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} = 1.25m$	$l_c = \frac{V_{OX\ Tank} - \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} = 4.31m$
Include 10cm for titanium caps	
$OAL = 2.35m$ $\phi_{fuel\ tank} = 1.0m$	$OAL = 5.28m$ $\phi_{oxi\ tank} = 1.0m$

Tank Masses are estimated using pV/W approach

$$\phi_{tank} = \frac{p_b \cdot V}{m_{tank} \cdot g_0}$$

$$m_{tank\ Fuel} \cong 27kg$$

$$m_{tank\ Ox} \cong 58kg$$

2.5.3. Pressurant System

Similar to Second-Stage consider the “Autogenous-Pressurization System” discussed previously. No external pressurant tankage will be required. However, we can assume using six (Electrically-driven Micro-pumps) capable of pumping both liquid and gas, along with electric power source to have;

$$mass_{micro-pumps} = 6 \times 400gm = 2.4kg$$

$$mass_{power\ unit} = 4.0kg$$

2.5.4. Masses of Thrust Vector Control (TVC), & Feed-System

Included in engine mass.

2.5.5. Structural Mounts Masses

Represents about 5-10% from main components masses. Calculated through;

$$0.1(m_E + m_{Propellant\ Tanks}) \approx 20kg$$

2.6. Mass Budget Summary

SECOND STAGE

<i>Component</i>	<i>Mass (kg)</i>	<i>Comments</i>
Liquid Propylene	54.5	$m_{prop} = 196$
Liquid Oxygen	141.5	
Engine + TVC + FEED-SYSTEM	13.6	
Fuel Tank	4.0	
LOX Tank	7.0	
Micro pumps	1.2	
Power Unit	3.0	
Structural Mounts	3.0	
Payload	90	
Total Wet	317.8	
Total Dry	31.8	Excluding propellant & payload
m_{inert} estimated	≈ 65	For $f_{inert} = 0.25$
Mass expected for structure $\sim 32.2kg$		

total weight assumed for Second Stage will be 350kg including Design Margin.

FIRST STAGE

<i>Component</i>	<i>Mass (kg)</i>	<i>Comments</i>
Liquid Propylene	1557.6	$m_{prop} = 5607.2kg$
Liquid Oxygen	4049.6	
Engine + TVC + FEED-SYSTEM	124	For the three "LP-1" Engines with design margin.
Fuel Tank	27.0	
LOX Tank	58.0	
Micro pumps	2.4	
Power Unit	4.0	
Structural Mounts	20.0	
Payload	350	Second-Stage (+design margin)
Total Wet	6192.6	
Total Dry	235.4	Excluding propellant & payload
m_{inert} estimated	554.5	$f_{inert} = 0.09$
Mass expected for structure $\sim 311kg$		

Table 4 Mass Budget: First Stage - Second Stage

2.7. Components Dimensions Summary

Component ALL DIMENSIONS IN (cm)	STAGE-1		STAGE-2		Comments
	Overall length	∅	Overall length	∅	
FUEL TANK	235	100	63	43	
LOX TANK	505	100	113	43	
ENGINE L_E	32.8		53.5		
ENGINE D_E	18.2		28.8		
Outer Diameter	120		64		
Interstage height	150				
Overall height	16,900				According to user's guide

Table 5 Launcher Dimensions Summary

2.8. Mass Properties Summary

	COMPONENT	MASS	COM x-axis aligned	I_{xx}	I_{yy}	I_{zz}
		kg	mm	kg.m ²	kg.m ²	kg.m ²
FIRST STAGE	3x LP-1 Engines	124	--	--	--	--
	FUEL-LP	1557.6	1970	329.73	951.64	951.64
	Fuel Tank Structure	115.56	1970			
	LOX	4049.6	6210	927.80	10779.89	10779.89
	LOX Tank Structure	300.44	6210			
	INTERSTAGE	30				
SECOND STAGE	LP-2 Engine	13.6	--	--	--	--
	LOX	141.5	11670	4.74	31.21	31.21
	LOX Tank Structure	44.9	11670			
	FUEL-LP	54.5	12750	3.71	10.86	10.86
	Fuel Tank Structure	17.29	12750			
	Payload & Fairing	90				

Table 6 Launcher Mass Properties and Center of Mass

3. Structural Loading

Various mechanical (structural) loads are considered and analyzed to ensure the structure and structural components are able not only to survive, but also to protect internal nonstructural components and allow proper functioning. Structural loads differ according to the environment, from Ground Environment, to Launch Environment, until Space Environment and its different phases.

The main points in the *Ground Environment Loading* are *Vehicle Integration, Ground Handling and Transportation*. As seen in the photos of Vector-R integration process, Figure 6, it is noticed that due to the lightweight and compact nature of the all composite launcher, it is required to have many interconnecting parts of the vehicle and ensure perfect elements integration within a very small space. As for the *Ground Handling, Transportation, and Launch Pad*, additional parts are added as shown in figure 5. These parts will not be analyzed in this report due to the tight scope of this course project.

A variety of dynamic loads are present within the Launch Environment and Space Environment. Relatively minor dynamic loads shall be considered within the Ground Environment. More insight will be gained about the dynamic loading in the following sections.

3.1. Static Airframe Loads

Static loads are mechanical structural loads that can be external or self-contained. Examples for this type of loading are;

- Static, external loading – the weight of supported components during launcher integration. Mass loading of the structure itself. When uniform is referred to as quasi-static, such as from gravity or steady acceleration. [12]
- Static, internal loads – pressure of stored propellant; mechanical preloads, as in parts integration and tightening; thermoelastic loads, due to fueling the tanks with subcooled propellant for example.

3.2. Dynamic Loads

During the lift-off phase critical dynamic loads, that vary with time, appear due to the sudden application thrust force and redistribution of loads inside the vehicle. Further, during the flight phase, aerodynamic loads take place in forms of *Drag forces* and *Lift Forces* and *Aerodynamic pressures*. At the time the launcher reaches a relatively high speed combined with decreasing in air density, maximum aerodynamic loads occur, termed *Maximum Dynamic Pressure*, which is proportional to ($\propto \rho u^2$) the air density and vehicle's square speed. Vehicle maneuverability, also termed as *Steering*, induces significant bending and torsional loads on the structure of the launcher.

To summarize, examples of dynamic loading are;

- Dynamic, external loads – Engine Thrust, sound pressure, wind gusts during launch; Pulsed thrust in case of orbital injection/positioning; Transportation vibrations in the ground environment phase [12].
- Dynamic, internal loads – dynamic response of vibrating internal parts of the launcher after the exciting force was removed. This can occur in all environments.

These loads may be analyzed by two methods:

- i. Replacing the dynamic load by an *Equivalent Static Load*.
- ii. In case of large fluctuating forces and repeated loading patterns, *Fatigue Analysis* is used.

3.3. Loading Cases

For the structural analysis carried in this report, loading conditions at different scenarios during launch phase are considered. These scenarios shall exhibit the loading conditions that would qualify the designed parts of the launcher. In other words, considering factors of safety to the *Flight limit Loads* in order to have proper *Design Loads* that will consequently define Yield Loads, Ultimate Loads, and Buckling Loads [13].

Loading Scenarios:

- 1) **Pre Lift-off (Fixed Support case);** Pure Axial Loads, Full Tanks Mass. Takes place during ignition and throttling phases at time T[+1s, +4.7s]. At which the Launcher acquires almost 60KN thrust before reaching >1g necessary for lift-off.
- 2) **Lift-off (Weak Springs case);** Pure Axial Loads, almost Full Tanks Mass. Takes place during actual lift-off phase at time T[+4.7s, +8s]. When the launcher acquires about 1.3g Thrust to Weight ratio necessary for lifting off from the launch pad.
- 3) **Pitch-Kick phase;** Axial, Torsion, and Bending Moments are significant along with significantly reduce in first stage tanks masses. Takes place at time T[+20s, +35s]. Pitch kick uses thrust vectoring to orient the launcher to the required Azimuth and Elevation.
- 4) **Max-Dynamic Pressure phase;** significant different types of Vibrations and structural loads takes place when the launcher enters the maximum dynamic pressure zone, where the aerodynamic structural load *is proportional* to dynamic pressure. Takes place during time T[+45s, 65s].

As for the results included in this report, scenario (1) & (2) were only simulated in Ansys Workbench.

3.4. Margins of Safety

Margin of Safety and Factor of Safety have different meanings. Actually, the MoS depends on FoS, while FoS is used to determine the reliability of the structure [Wijker 2007]. The MoS can be defined as:

$$MoS = \frac{\sigma_{allowable}}{j \cdot \sigma_{actual}} - 1$$

Where, $\sigma_{allowable}$ denotes the ultimate stress of the material (max stress to be applied without breakage), σ_{actual} is the actual stress due to designed limit load, and j is the *factor of safety*, usually denoted with a subscript to identify the specified load type in relation to Flight Limit Loads, as shown in figure (13).

Margin of Safety	Significance
MoS < 0	Failure
0 < MoS < 0.5	Optimal Design
0.5 < MoS < 1.5	Good Design
<u>MoS > 1.5</u>	<u>Design can be easily improved</u>

Table 7 Margins of Safety significance. [Wijker 2007]

In this study, High MoS have always been considered, since this is a preliminary design phase and a lot of room for improvement, and iterative design and analysis must be taken in account.

As for the factors of safety, the following flowchart shall show the relationship between factors of safety and designated loads. In the following report chapters this scheme shall be used to designate proper Factors of Safety.

The results obtained by ANSYS Composites ACP for MoS & FoS are shown in chapter 4 of this report. The failure study displays the critical safety factor and margin of safety to first ply failure. The FoS are evaluated for every element and every layer and the critical value through the thickness of layups is then projected on the reference shell mesh.

Figure 13 Factors of Safety and Loads relationship. Courtesy to Wijker 2007

Option	Factors of Safety			
	Critical for Personnel Safety		Not Critical for Personnel Safety	
	Yield	Ultimate	Yield	Ultimate
1) Test a dedicated article to ultimate loads (<i>ultimate test, or static qualification test</i>)	1.1	1.4	1.1	1.25
2) Proof test all flight structures to 1.1 times limit	1.1	1.4	1.1	1.25
3) Test one flight unit of a fleet to 1.25 times limit (protoflight)	1.25	1.4	1.25	1.4
4) No structural test	1.6	2.25	1.6	2.0

Table 8 Recommended Factors of Safety. [Sarafin 1997]

3.5. Launch Simulation & Flight Loads

Flight simulation process was carried with opensource online user-defined simulator (*FLIGHT CLUB® The Orbital Launch Simulator and Trajectory Visualization Software*). Designed Launcher parameters, see chapter 2, were used to simulate the Launch of the Vehicle until the orbital insertion of the payload. Assumed launch site is *Mid-Atlantic Regional Spaceport - MARS WALLOPS* with *Latitude 37.83°*, *Longitude -75.48°*, and *Zero elevation*. (Images taken from the simulator GUI will be attached in the *Flight Simulation Appendix*.)

Following are numeric results obtained from the simulator. Graph [1] shows *Altitude vs Time*, and typically ends at 250km insertion point as intended in the launcher design study. Graphs [5 & 8] shows *Acceleration & Thrust*, both vs *Time* and these data were used in the *Structural Analysis Study* carried in chapter 4. Graph [12] shows *ΔV expenditure vs Time* and proves feasibility of Launcher *Preliminary Design* carried in chapter 2 with almost similar results.

Figure 14 snapshot from 3D Flight Simulation of the Designed Launcher. End of red trajectory represents Micro-satellite Payload Separation.

<https://www2.flightclub.io/result/3d?id=f1a34014-b194-47de-b10f-6e02d48f12f5>

Graphs [1 – 8]
 Green: Stage-2 Blue: Stage-1

Graphs [9 - 16]
Green: Stage-2 Blue: Stage-1

Graphs [17 – 18]

Flight Dynamics Simulation performed by (The Orbital Launch Simulator and Trajectory Visualization Software) <https://www2.flightclub.io/>

2D & 3D simulation results can be accessed using this link:

<https://www2.flightclub.io/result/2d?id=2ec1f3b6-6d4d-4246-81c2-a55acf58d04a>

4. Structural Analysis - ANSYS® Workbench

4.1. Theoretical Background

4.1.1. Analysis Philosophy

Finite Element Analysis is used to study and investigate the Unibody Structure of the LOX Propellant Tank of the Launcher. The structure of the LOX Tank is the biggest self-standing structure on the launcher. A crucial component to verify its *strengths properties* and to study its *dynamic analysis and response*. Thus, this particular Unibody structural design modification and refinement must have a high priority compared to other propellant tanks and launcher parts.

4.1.2. Analysis Types

Types of analyses performed using finite element method are, *Static Structural Analysis*, *Linear-Buckling Analysis*, and *Modal Analysis*. The first type aims to verify the strengths properties of the structural elements. The stresses/loads on elements are verified and compared to the allowable stresses/loads to show intended high values of margins of safety. As for the second analysis type, it will output the allowable buckling stresses/loads, as well as the modes of buckling (shapes & patterns) after the structure's failure. The last analysis type, Modal Analysis, is a dynamic analysis that outputs the natural frequencies and the associated mode shapes. Modal Analysis is used to determine the vibration characteristics of the structure which can be used to understand the possible resonance occurrence and avoiding it.

4.1.3. Large Deflections analysis method

It is important to note that, static solutions can be *Linear or Nonlinear solutions*. Linear solutions are based on basic principles of mechanics of materials dealing with *homogeneous isotropic* materials, which include most metal alloys. *Composite materials* – are *nonhomogeneous*, with *anisotropic* properties. Nonlinearities in structures are of two general types: *Material Nonlinearities*, in which relationship between stress and strain is nonlinear, and *Geometrical Nonlinearities*, in which the structure's deforming geometry creates new load paths, which is the case when Large Deflection analysis setting is used in FEA software. FEA can handle nonlinearity but they require iterative solutions and considerable computer time [SARAFIN 1997, Sec. 16.2], especially when large number of nodes (high DOFs) exist.

At this point it is worthy to highlight the fundamental definition of *statically indeterminate structure*, the one that provides more load paths than are necessary to satisfy equilibrium; thus, we cannot determine deflections, internal loads and stresses solely with equilibrium equations. In most cases, finite-element modeling is the most efficient way to analyze indeterminate – nonlinear – structures.

4.1.4. Methods of Introducing Loads in FEA

Nodal degrees of freedom are the basis of finite-element analysis, so all forces, displacements and temperatures must be applied at nodes. Each node possesses 6-DOFs, three translations and 3 rotations, and the whole structure's DOFs is thus determined by calculating number of nodes.

Inertia loading is a way to statically load a finite-element model. The uniform acceleration can be simulated by specifying a Load Factor – n , or multiple of Earth's gravitational acceleration, g , and a direction opposite that of the acceleration, as illustrated in Fig 15.

Figure 15 A Load Factor Represents Inertia Force as Dimensionless Multiple of g 's – in opposite direction

The nodal inertia forces are computed in FEA by

$$\{F\} = g [M]\{n\}$$

Where $\{F\}$: is the vector of applied forces; g : is the gravitational acceleration; $[M]$: is the mass matrix; $\{n\}$: is the vector of load factors; [Sarafin Sec 3.1].

Again, note that, for *static solutions*, without enough DOFs being constrained (grounded), static equilibrium will not be achieved, and stiffness matrix singularity will occur; [Sarafin Sec 16.2].

To avoid this problem, the next paragraph will introduce *weak-springs analysis method*.

4.1.5. Weak Springs analysis method

But what if it is necessary to perform an under-constrained analysis – where rigid body motion will occur – as the case in one of the analyses scenarios in this report. The answer lies in the Weak Springs analysis setting, where FEA software allows performing the analysis solely with the externally applied forces and inertial forces without the need of motion-fixing supports. In the case of Weak Springs, the simulator mimics the action of springs holding the structure to overcome the rigid body motion problem. However, the weak springs effect will not alter the results of simulation. One important property was investigated and practiced in this report, is the Stiffness setting of the Weak Spring method. The stiffness is either changed by a numeric value with (N/mm) dimensions, or with a Factor multiple of 1. By changing the stiffness value, it was able to acquire the simulation results with least translations possible – translations were reduced from 30m to only 1350mm in axial direction, and nearly 50mm in transversal directions – thus, obtaining accurate results in the *Total Deformation test*.

4.2. Static Structural Analysis

A static structural analysis determines displacement, strains, and stresses in structures and components caused by applied loads. Static analysis can be linear or nonlinear according to the relation between applied forces and displacements. In a linear static analysis, the model's stiffness matrix remains constant. As for a nonlinear static analysis – caused by either material nonlinearity, geometrical nonlinearity, or constraint nonlinearity – the stiffness matrix is no longer constant during load application.

For static analyses the equilibrium equations are derived using minimum principle of potential energy, and equations of motion are derived using Lagrangian mechanics; [Wijker 2007 Sec. 11.2].

Briefly stating the theory; given a function u , a kinematic displacement function, chosen to make the total potential energy $V(u)$ stationary,

$$\delta V(u) = 0$$

The *potential energy* is given by:

$$V(u) = U(u) - W(u)$$

$$U \text{ is the strain energy, } U = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \{\varepsilon\}^T [C] \{\varepsilon\} dV$$

W is the work done by external load vector $\{F\}$,

$$W = \int_V \{F\}^T \{u\} dV$$

$\{\varepsilon\}$ is the strain vector, $[C]$ is matrix of constitutive relations, V is the volume, and the stress vector $\{\sigma\} = [C]\{\varepsilon\}$.

For a single element in a finite-element ensemble, the displacement (shape) function

$$u_e = [H]\{\delta_e\}$$

Where the vector $\{\delta_e\}$ represents the displacements and the rotations in the nodes of the element, and $[H]$ is the nodes position matrix.

The stiffness matrix of the finite element can be defined as

$$[K_e] = \int_{V_e} \{B\}^T [C_e] \{B\} dV_e$$

Where $\{B\}$ is the strain-displacement vector, and $[C_e]$ is the constitutive matrix for an element.

This brief introduction is sufficient to grasp the idea behind the calculation method carried on in the static structural analysis of the FEA, more details can be found in [Wijker 2007 - Sec 11.2].

4.3. Buckling Analysis

4.3.1. Buckling of Isotropic Unstiffened Unpressurized Cylinder in Axial Compression:

Buckling and collapse coincide for the *isotropic circular cylinder* in axial compression. For moderately long cylinder the buckling equation in axial stress can be expressed as;

$$\sigma_x = \frac{\gamma E}{\sqrt{3(1-\mu^2)}} \frac{t}{r}$$

With factor γ taken as

$$\gamma = 1 - 0.901 (1 - e^{-\phi})$$

$$\phi = \frac{1}{16} \sqrt{\frac{r}{t}}$$

4.3.2. Buckling of Isotropic Unstiffened Pressurized Cylinders in Axial Compression:

For circular cylinders subjected to axial compression, internal pressurization increases the buckling load in following ways [NASA SP-8007] [14]:

1. The total compressive-load must be larger than tensile pressurization load $p\pi r^2$ before buckling occurs.
2. The destabilizing effects of initial imperfections are decreased. Circumferential tensile stress induced by the pressurization inhibits the diamond buckling pattern, and at sufficiently high pressurization the cylinder buckles in the classical axisymmetric mode at approximately the classical buckling stress.

The total load for buckling can be obtained by

$$P_{press} = 2\pi Et^2 \left(\frac{\gamma}{\sqrt{3(1-\mu^2)}} + \Delta\gamma \right) + p\pi r^2$$

E: Young's modulus

t: skin thickness

μ : Poisson's ration

$p\pi r^2$: pressurization load

Where $\Delta\gamma$ is the increase in buckling correlation factor due to internal pressure and is obtained from the following figure.

Figure 16 increase in axial-compressive buckling-stress coefficient of cylinders due to internal pressure.

4.3.3. Buckling for Orthotropic (Stiffened) Cylinders

In material science, orthotropic materials have properties that differ along three mutually-orthogonal axes of rotational symmetry at a particular point. They are a subset of anisotropic materials, because their properties change when measured from different directions.

The term "Orthotropic materials" denotes cylinders made of single orthotropic material or of orthotropic multiple layers. It also denotes types of stiffened cylinders where the stiffener spacing is small enough for the cylinder to be approximated by a fictitious sheet whose orthotropic bending and extensional properties include those of the individual stiffening elements average out

over a specified area. Generally, the direction of orthotropic axes coincides with axial and circumferential directions of the cylinder. [NASA SP-8007]

A Buckling equation for *stiffened orthotropic cylinders in compression* is given by

$$N_x = \left(\frac{\ell}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{\begin{vmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33} \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{vmatrix}} \quad \text{for } n \geq 4$$

Where ℓ : length of cylinder

m : number of buckle half waves in the axial direction

n : number of buckle waves in in the circumferential direction.

G : Shear modulus

D : wall *flexural stiffness* per unit width $\frac{Et^3}{12(1-\mu^2)}$

The values of m and n to be used for given cylinder and stiffener dimensions. While A_{ij} is function of E, G, D, m, n and are found in detail in reference [NASA] equations [38-43].

The previously discussed theory of buckling is applicable for circular cylindrical shells. More detailed discussion for laminated composite shells, and the different properties of plies orientation can be obtained from [J. N. Reddy – 2003, “Mechanics of Laminated Composite Plates and Shells”.]

4.4. Modal Analysis

When *dynamic analyses* are concerned for finite-element models, besides the *potential energy* $V(u)$, the *kinetic energy* $T(\dot{u})$, the *damping energy* $D(u, \dot{u}, \dots)$, and the *work* done by applied forces $W(F, u)$ all must be considered. For a *damped dynamic system*, the equations of motion can be expressed by

$$[M]\{\ddot{\delta}\} + [D]\{\dot{\delta}\} + [K]\{\delta\} = \{F\}$$

The equations of motion can be derived using Lagrangian mechanics briefly as follows [13];

First, assume an undamped dynamic system. For a displacement function u , the *Lagrangian function (Kinetic Potential)* $L(u, \dot{u})$ is defined as

$$L(u, \dot{u}) = T(\dot{u}) - V(u)$$

The equations of Lagrange without damping can be expressed as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L(u, \dot{u})}{\partial \dot{u}} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial L(u, \dot{u})}{\partial u} \right) = \frac{\delta W(F, u)}{\delta u}$$

Where the virtual work done by the external forces is $\delta W(F, u)$.

The kinetic energy for a finite-element $T_e(\dot{u})$ is

$$T_e(\dot{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_e} m(x, y, z) \dot{u}_e^2(x, y, z) dV_e$$

$$V_e(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{V_e} \{\varepsilon_e\}^T [C_e] \{\varepsilon_e\} dV_e - \int_{V_e} \{F_e\}^T \{u_e\} dV_e$$

Where, $V_e(u)$ is the potential energy for an element, and W_e is the work done by external load vector $\{F_e\}$.

The Lagrangian function for the entire undamped dynamic system is given by:

$$L(u, \dot{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \{\dot{\delta}\}^T [M] \{\dot{\delta}\} - \frac{1}{2} \{\delta\}^T [K] \{\delta\}$$

The Mass Matrix: $[M] \{\ddot{\delta}\} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L(u, \dot{u})}{\partial \dot{u}} \right)$

The Stiffness Matrix: $[K] \{\delta\} = - \frac{\partial L(u)}{\partial u}$

Finally, after extracting the force vector from the virtual work, the undamped equations of motion of the dynamic system are presented by

$$[M] \{\ddot{\delta}\} + [K] \{\delta\} = \{F\}$$

4.5. ANSYS ACP Composite Analysis System

- **Composite Prep/Post (ACP)**

ANSYS Composite PrepPost (ACP) is an add-in to ANSYS Workbench and is integrated with the standard analysis features. The entire workflow for composite structure can be completed from design to final information production as a result. ACP has a pre- and post-processing mode. In the pre-processing mode, all composite definitions can be created and are mapped to the geometry (FE mesh). These composite definitions are transferred to the FE model and the solver input file. In the post-processing mode, after a completed solution and the import of the result file(s), post-processing results (failure, safety, strains and stresses) can be evaluated and visualized [15]. Typical project scheme for a composite structure analysis using ACP is shown in the following figure.

Figure 17 Project Scheme of Composites Analysis using ACP PrepPost

- **ACP PrepPost Process Summary**

1. Add ACP (Pre) component to the project
2. Define Engineering Data
3. Import Geometry
4. Open Model and:
 - a. Define Named Selections/Element Sets
 - b. Generate Mesh
5. Open ACP (Pre) and:
 - a. Define Fabric
 - b. Define Rosettes & Oriented Element Sets
 - c. Create Modeling Plies
6. Add Analysis system (Static, Buckling, Modal, ...)
7. Open Analysis System and:
 - a. Define Analysis settings
 - b. Define Boundary conditions
 - c. Solve model

4.6. ANSYS Analysis Results – Complete Unibody Structure of LOX S1 Tank

4.6.1. Static Structural Analysis Results

In this section, results of static structural analysis, Total deformation, Equivalent Stresses and Strains will be presented and discussed for the complete unibody structure of the LOX tank of the first-stage of the launch vehicle. the project scheme is shown in figure (18).

Figure 18 Complete Unibody Structure of S1-LOX Tank – Project scheme

Project Tree

The project tree -fig (19), shows the full unibody structure components consisting of, the pressure vessel (Tank), inner tube, stiffeners, and outer wrap. Point mass is added to the pressure vessel structure, the rest of body components are glued together using proper contacts that will be discussed in the connections paragraph.

Note that the Titanium Tanks Caps were suppressed during the analysis due to their great number of nodes that required very long analysis time.

Analysis was carried on over night, typically more than 6 hours for all the shown solutions.

In figure (20), applied forces directions and values can be seen. Discussion of Loading Scenarios is present in section 3.3 of this report.

Figure (21) shows components meshing, high mesh resolution (high number of elements & nodes) were used as much as possible to limit analysis time, since the structure is made of nonlinear – composite – materials and large deflections must take place in order for the analysis to run without errors and output reliable result.

Care was taken in applying connections to different parts, especially when contacting the stiffeners with the surrounding tubes. It is important to set each contact *shell face manually* and account for *shell thickness effect* in order to ensure the analysis runs without abnormalities. All types of contact used are of *symmetric behaviour* and *Bonded Type*, refer to figures (22, 23, 24).

Figure 19 Project Tree for the complete Unibody Structure of S1-LOX Tank

“Structural Analyses results are present in the following sections with details mentioned on each figure and/or illustrated in figure caption when applicable.”

Force Application & Mesh details

Figure 20 Complete Loading Settings in Unibody Structure of S1-LOX Tank

Figure 21 Components Meshing

Contacts and Connections

Figure 22 Connection between Innertube & Stiffeners

Details of "Contact Region 3"

Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Contact	1 Face
Target	1 Face
Contact Bodies	INNER_TUBE(V1.4 INNER_TUBE - ACP (Pre))
Target Bodies	LONGT_STRINGER(V1.4 LONGITUDINAL ...)
Contact Shell Face	Top
Target Shell Face	Bottom
Shell Thickness Effect	Yes
Protected	No
Definition	
Type	Bonded
Scope Mode	Automatic
Behavior	Symmetric
Trim Contact	Program Controlled
Trim Tolerance	14.229 mm
Suppressed	No

Figure 23 Details of Contact Regions – Connections

Figure 24 Contacts between Pressure Vessel and Innertube

TOTAL DEFORMATION

Figure 25 Total Deformation of Complete Unibody Structure of S1-LOX Tank. It is important to mention that the least Translation achieved during this (Weak Spring analysis type with Factor 6 for spring stiffness) was 1959mm. The results show Relative Deformation of ~0.5mm which is realistic when compared to the results of other loading cases with (fixed support or simply-support boundaries)

EQUIVALENT STRESS

Figure 26 Equivalent (Von-Mises) Stress – Complete Unibody Structure

EQUIVALENT ELASTIC STRAIN

Figure 27 Equivalent Elastic Strain – Complete Unibody Structure

AFT STRUCTURE STRESS

Figure 28 Aft (Backside) Equivalent Stress in the Unibody structure case, showing critical values on the Tank part. The last figure shows stress in different layers of the pressure vessel.

FRONT STRUCTURE STRESS

Figure 29 Front side Equivalent Stress of Unibody structure case.

AFT ELASTIC STRAIN

Figure 30 Aft side Equivalent Elastic Strain of the Unibody structure case

FRONT ELASTIC STRAIN

Figure 31 Front side Equivalent Elastic Strain of the Unibody structure case

STIFFENERS STRESS (AFT - FRONT)

Figure 32 Stiffeners Equivalent Stress values shown in the Aft (top) and Front (bottom) sides of the Unibody structure case.

STIFFENERS ELASTIC STRAIN (AFT-FRONT)

Figure 33 Stiffeners Elastic Strain values shown in the Aft (top) and Front (bottom) sides of the Unibody structure case.

4.6.2. Buckling Analysis Results

Figure 34 Figures showing Modes 1 & 2 of the Buckling. Note the Load Multiplier values are almost 2 (two times applied test load is required to induce linear buckling in the structure). This value will decrease in the cases of Only Outer Structure and Only Pressure vessel and will be shown in following sections, this indicate the Stabilizing Effect gained from the Unibody Structural Design). Note that modes 3&4 are only translations without buckling failure (due to Weak Spring analysis setting)

SECTION VIEW – TRUE SCALE

Figure 35 Section view with true scale (unamplified) deformation

4.6.3. Modal Analysis Results

Figure 36 first 6 Modal shapes (translations and rotations) show deformation of <1mm.

SECTION VIEW – TRUE SCALE

4.7. ANSYS Analysis Results – Pressure Vessel

4.7.1. Static Structural Analysis Results

TOTAL DEFORMATION

Figure 37 Pressure Vessel static analysis, applying MEOP with safety margin =1.5MPa, showing max deformation of 0.55mm in red zones.

EQUIVALENT STRESS

Figure 38 Equivalent Stress in the Pressure Vessel under 1.5MPa.

EQUIVALENT ELASTIC STRAIN

Figure 39 Equivalent Elastic Strain of Pressure Vessel under 1.5MPa.

4.7.2. Buckling Analysis Results

Figure 40 Buckling of Pressure Vessel under 1.5MPa, Load Multiplier value of ~1.3 is achieved.

SECTION VIEW – TRUE SCALE

4.7.3. Modal Analysis Results

4.8. ANSYS Analysis Results – Outer Body Structure

4.8.1. Static Structural Analysis Results

SECTION VIEW – TRUE SCALE

4.8.2. Buckling Analysis Results

Figure 41 Buckling Modes 1&2 of the outer structure carried out under the loading scenario of Pre-liftoff with fixed support boundary condition (see section 3.3). Testing Load is 80kN ($j_B=1.33$) showing buckling failure with 1mm deformation at Load Multiplier ~ 74 . It is worthy to mention that the Launcher will be subjected to 60kN before exceeding lift-off thrust to weight ratio.

Figure 42 Buckling Modes 3&4 of the outer structure carried out under the loading scenario of Pre-liftoff with fixed support boundary condition (see section 3.3). Testing Load is 80kN ($j_B=1.33$) showing buckling failure with 1mm deformation at Load Multiplier ~ 77 . It is worthy to mention that the Launcher will be subjected to 60kN before exceeding lift-off thrust to weight ratio.

4.8.3. Modal Analysis Results

MARGINS OF SAFETY & FACTORS OF SAFETY

ACP (Pre) Setup (applies for all Composite Components)

The ACP (Pre) Setup is used to define the properties of the composite structure, either the Materials, Fabric properties, Stackups properties, and the Plies orientation and direction of application.

In the Model-tree figure (43), it is important to first define the Materials, Steel is present by default but should be neglected in our case. We proceed by choosing the Epoxy Carbon Woven (395GPA) Prepreg that Fabrics and Stackups will be built upon.

Secondly, Element Sets are defined, this is crucial if we have a structure with different elements and we need to define different material properties to different materials sets. However, in our case, each part has consisted material. The Fabric with is the building block of Plies or Stackups shall be defined in terms of material and thickness mainly. Following, the Stackups are defined in number of Plies and Plies' orientation as shown in figure (44).

Stackup of Plies are collected within Modeling Groups. Each modeling ply, within this modeling group, is defined by Oriented Selection Set and Ply name or Stackup name created previously.

Plies Orientation can be viewed in figure (45).

Figure 43 ACP-Pre Model-Tree

An *Oriented Selection Set* is an Element Set with additional information about the element orientations. The orientation direction of an Element Set is responsible for setting the stacking direction of the associated lay-up. The Reference Direction is responsible for setting the 0° direction of the associated layup. The laminate is modeled by defining different Oriented Selection Sets for the different regions.

Rosettes are coordinate systems that used to set the Reference Direction of Oriented Selection Sets. Rosettes define the 0° direction for the composite lay-up. Coordinate systems defined in Mechanical are imported by default. Additional Rosettes can be defined in ACP. There are different types of rosettes (Cylindrical, Spherical, Edge, ...etc.). The origin and directions of Rosettes are given in the global coordinate system.

Figure 44 Fabric Properties (top) - Stackup Properties (bottom)

Figure 45 Plies Orientation - Woven case and Unidirectional Case.

Conclusion

In this report, a commercial Launcher was explored and investigated (in chapter 1) considering its launch and payload orbital insertion capabilities. Structure of this commercial launcher was thoroughly investigated and studied from relevant published research work and patented technical data. Accordingly, *Materials Analysis study* was carried out along with the *Manufacturing Processes & Techniques* which were presented in sections 1.5 & 1.6. Chapter 2 covered the *Mission Analysis study* and *Liquid Propulsion System Analysis and Design*, iterations and tradeoff studies were made, and the chapter was concluded with the *Mass Budget & Mass Properties data*. The Mass Budget data and Propulsion System properties were then imported in the *Orbital Launch Simulator and Trajectory Visualization Software* in order to *validate the preliminary design* made for the *propulsion system and rocket design study*. Data were collected showing successful launch and payload orbital insertion. Consequently, *Flight Data* were acquired from the simulator software and analyzed to detect *Flight Loading Conditions and Loading Scenarios*, and this concluded chapter 3.

Structural Analysis was performed using finite-element method by ANSYS software. Due to *nonlinearities* in the structure – either caused by the nonlinear material properties of composites due to their anisotropic nature or caused by geometrical nonlinearities, – as well as the *under-constrained nature of the structure analysis*, the use of *advanced structural analysis methods* was unavoidable. Such advanced analysis methods are *Large Deflections*, and *Weak Springs* analysis methods. A deep study for these analysis settings was made and verified by small-scale tests before being implemented in full-scale. Section 4.1 explains intensively the theory behind the analysis.

Structural analyses (*Static, Linear-Buckling, and Modal*) were carried out on the *Unibody Structure of S-1 LOX Tank*, for the reason it is the largest in terms of mass and size, which makes it a crucial part in the analysis and design process of the whole launcher. Chapter 4 shows results of the structural analysis for the *Complete Unibody Structure*, the *Pressure Vessel alone*, and the *Outer-structure alone*. First and second *Loading Scenarios*, discussed in section 3.3, were performed with promising analysis results (least Margin of Safety is >5) that would allow a great room for structure optimization and mass reduction, only after performing more verification tests with the rest of loading scenarios. Chapter 4 was concluded with a summary for *ANSYS Composites ACP* simulation system setup and composite *Plies* layout and design.

Future Work

- Testing the rest of *Loading Cases* discussed in section 3.3
- Structure optimization and mass reduction to maintain reasonably lower Margin of Safety.
- Add *Slosh Baffles* to the internal structure of the propellant tank.
- Add the stainless-steel rings acting like *interconnecting components* with rest of launcher parts.
- Perform similar structural analyses on other unibody propellant tanks in the launcher.

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APPENDIX

A. MASS PROPERTIES

NOTE:

(EMPTY) Depicts the mass properties of according to structure mass assigned by Solidworks according to selection materials. Care has to be taken because some parts materials either are not accurate or are left material-less.

(FUELED) Depicts the overridden mass according to my preliminary design results listed in the mass budget section. Overridden mass is assigned without considering any mass considerations of the EMPTY model according to Solidworks.

Mass properties of ASSEMBLY_FULL_LAUNCHER_FUELED

Configuration: Default

Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass = 6482.47 kilograms

Volume = 2.69 cubic meters

Surface area = 287.42 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 5.55

Y = 0.00

Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

$I_x = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)$

$P_x = 1939.33$

$I_y = (0.00, 1.00, 0.00)$

$P_y = 69412.46$

$I_z = (0.00, 0.00, 1.00)$

$P_z = 69426.02$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

$L_{xx} = 1939.33$

$L_{xy} = -0.01$

$L_{xz} = -0.06$

$L_{yx} = -0.01$

$L_{yy} = 69412.46$

$L_{yz} = 0.00$

$L_{zx} = -0.06$

$L_{zy} = 0.00$

$L_{zz} = 69426.02$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

$l_{xx} = 1939.33$

$l_{xy} = -0.03$

$l_{xz} = -0.11$

$l_{yx} = -0.03$

$l_{yy} = 268952.58$

$l_{yz} = 0.00$

$l_{zx} = -0.11$

$l_{zy} = 0.00$

$l_{zz} = 268966.13$

One or more components have overridden mass properties:

Assem_S2_LOX_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL@Assem_S2_AIRFRAME

Assem_S2_FUEL_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL@Assem_S2_AIRFRAME

FULL_Assem_S1_Fuel_Tank

FULL_Assem_S1_LOX_TANK

The center of mass and the moments of inertia are output in the coordinate system of ASSEMBLY_FULL_LAUNCHER
 Mass = 230.35 kilograms

Mass properties of FULL_Assem_S1_Fuel_Tank (EMPTY)

Configuration: Default
 Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass (user-overridden) = 115.56 kilograms

Volume = 0.12 cubic meters

Surface area = 50.19 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 1.97
 Y = 0.00
 Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

$I_x = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)$	$P_x = 24.05$
$I_y = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)$	$P_y = 69.40$
$I_z = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)$	$P_z = 69.40$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

$L_{xx} = 24.05$	$L_{xy} = 0.00$	$L_{xz} = 0.00$
$L_{yx} = 0.00$	$L_{yy} = 69.40$	$L_{yz} = 0.00$
$L_{zx} = 0.00$	$L_{zy} = 0.00$	$L_{zz} = 69.40$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

$I_{xx} = 24.05$	$I_{xy} = 0.00$	$I_{xz} = 0.00$
$I_{yx} = 0.00$	$I_{yy} = 515.67$	$I_{yz} = 0.00$
$I_{zx} = 0.00$	$I_{zy} = 0.00$	$I_{zz} = 515.67$

Mass properties of FULL_Assem_S1_Fuel_Tank (FUELED)

Configuration: Default

Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass (user-overridden) = 1673.16 kilograms

Volume = 0.12 cubic meters

Surface area = 50.19 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 1.97

Y = 0.00

Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

lx = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)

Px = 348.15

ly = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)

Py = 1004.82

lz = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)

Pz = 1004.82

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

Lxx = 348.15

Lxy = 0.00

Lxz = 0.00

Lyx = 0.00

Lyy = 1004.82

Lyz = 0.00

Lzx = 0.00

Lzy = 0.00

Lzz = 1004.82

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

lxx = 348.15

lxy = 0.00

lxz = 0.00

lyx = 0.00

lyy = 7466.28

lyz = 0.00

lzx = 0.00

lzy = 0.00

lzz = 7466.28

The center of mass and the moments of inertia are output in the coordinate system of ASSEMBLY_FULL_LAUNCHER

Mass = 544.68 kilograms

Mass properties of FULL_Assem_S1_LOX_TANK (EMPTY)

Configuration: Default

Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass (user-overridden) = 300.44 kilograms

Volume = 0.29 cubic meters

Surface area = 116.09 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 6.21

Y = 0.00

Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

$I_x = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)$

$P_x = 67.86$

$I_y = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)$

$P_y = 788.47$

$I_z = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)$

$P_z = 788.47$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

$L_{xx} = 67.86$

$L_{xy} = 0.00$

$L_{xz} = 0.00$

$L_{yx} = 0.00$

$L_{yy} = 788.47$

$L_{yz} = 0.00$

$L_{zx} = 0.00$

$L_{zy} = 0.00$

$L_{zz} = 788.47$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

$I_{xx} = 67.86$

$I_{xy} = 0.00$

$I_{xz} = 0.00$

$I_{yx} = 0.00$

$I_{yy} = 12388.88$

$I_{yz} = 0.00$

$I_{zx} = 0.00$

$I_{zy} = 0.00$

$I_{zz} = 12388.88$

Mass properties of FULL_Assem_S1_LOX_TANK (FUELED)

Configuration: Default

Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass (user-overridden) = 4350.04 kilograms

Volume = 0.29 cubic meters

Surface area = 116.09 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 6.21

Y = 0.00

Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

lx = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)

Px = 982.56

ly = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)

Py = 11416.14

lz = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)

Pz = 11416.14

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

Lxx = 982.56

Lxy = 0.00

Lxz = 0.00

Lyx = 0.00

Lyy = 11416.14

Lyz = 0.00

Lzx = 0.00

Lzy = 0.00

Lzz = 11416.14

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

lxx = 982.56

lxy = 0.00

lxz = 0.00

lyx = 0.00

lyy = 179377.26

lyz = 0.00

lzx = 0.00

lzy = 0.00

lzz = 179377.26

The center of mass and the moments of inertia are output in the coordinate system of ASSEMBLY_FULL_LAUNCHER
 Mass = 179.40 kilograms

Mass properties of Assem_S2_AIRFRAME (EMPTY)

Configuration: Default
 Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass = 143.27 kilograms

Volume = 0.12 cubic meters

Surface area = 22.31 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 12.03
 Y = 0.00
 Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

$I_x = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)$	$P_x = 7.55$
$I_y = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)$	$P_y = 76.29$
$I_z = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)$	$P_z = 76.29$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

$L_{xx} = 7.55$	$L_{xy} = 0.00$	$L_{xz} = 0.00$
$L_{yx} = 0.00$	$L_{yy} = 76.29$	$L_{yz} = 0.00$
$L_{zx} = 0.00$	$L_{zy} = 0.00$	$L_{zz} = 76.29$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

$I_{xx} = 7.55$	$I_{xy} = -0.04$	$I_{xz} = -0.11$
$I_{yx} = -0.04$	$I_{yy} = 20824.11$	$I_{yz} = 0.00$
$I_{zx} = -0.11$	$I_{zy} = 0.00$	$I_{zz} = 20824.11$

One or more components have overridden mass properties:

Assem_S2_LOX_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL
 Assem_S2_FUEL_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL

Mass properties of Assem_S2_AIRFRAME (FUELED)

Configuration: Default

Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass = 339.27 kilograms

Volume = 0.12 cubic meters

Surface area = 22.31 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 12.00

Y = 0.00

Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

Ix = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)

Px = 13.44

Iy = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)

Py = 155.39

Iz = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)

Pz = 155.39

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

Lxx = 13.44

Lxy = 0.00

Lxz = 0.00

Lyx = 0.00

Lyy = 155.39

Lyz = 0.00

Lzx = 0.00

Lzy = 0.00

Lzz = 155.39

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

Ixx = 13.44

Ixy = -0.04

Ixz = -0.11

Iyx = -0.04

Iyy = 48997.45

Iyz = 0.00

Izx = -0.11

Izy = 0.00

Izz = 48997.45

One or more components have overridden mass properties:

Assem_S2_LOX_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL

Assem_S2_FUEL_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL

The center of mass and the moments of inertia are output in the coordinate system of ASSEMBLY_FULL_LAUNCHER
 Mass = 59.38 kilograms

Mass properties of Assem_S2_LOX_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL (EMPTY)

Configuration: Default
 Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass (user-overridden) = 44.90 kilograms

Volume = 0.03 cubic meters

Surface area = 8.75 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 11.67
 Y = 0.00
 Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

Ix = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)	Px = 1.43
Iy = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)	Py = 9.44
Iz = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)	Pz = 9.44

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

Lxx = 1.43	Lxy = 0.00	Lxz = 0.00
Lyx = 0.00	Lyy = 9.44	Lyz = 0.00
Lzx = 0.00	Lzy = 0.00	Lzz = 9.44

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

Ixx = 1.43	Ixy = 0.00	Ixz = 0.00
Iyx = 0.00	Iyy = 6129.45	Iyz = 0.00
Izx = 0.00	Izy = 0.00	Izz = 6129.45

Mass properties of Assem_S2_LOX_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL (FUELED)

Configuration: Default

Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass (user-overridden) = 186.40 kilograms

Volume = 0.03 cubic meters

Surface area = 8.75 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 11.67

Y = 0.00

Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

$I_x = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)$ $P_x = 5.96$

$I_y = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)$ $P_y = 39.17$

$I_z = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)$ $P_z = 39.17$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

$L_{xx} = 5.96$ $L_{xy} = 0.00$ $L_{xz} = 0.00$

$L_{yx} = 0.00$ $L_{yy} = 39.17$ $L_{yz} = 0.00$

$L_{zx} = 0.00$ $L_{zy} = 0.00$ $L_{zz} = 39.17$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

$I_{xx} = 5.96$ $I_{xy} = 0.00$ $I_{xz} = 0.00$

$I_{yx} = 0.00$ $I_{yy} = 25446.10$ $I_{yz} = 0.00$

$I_{zx} = 0.00$ $I_{zy} = 0.00$ $I_{zz} = 25446.10$

The center of mass and the moments of inertia are output in the coordinate system of ASSEMBLY_FULL_LAUNCHER
 Mass = 38.95 kilograms

Mass properties of Assem_S2_FUEL_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL (EMPTY)

Configuration: Default
 Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass (user-overridden) = 17.29 kilograms

Volume = 0.02 cubic meters

Surface area = 4.76 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 12.75
 Y = 0.00
 Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

$I_x = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)$	$P_x = 0.43$
$I_y = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)$	$P_y = 1.26$
$I_z = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)$	$P_z = 1.26$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

$L_{xx} = 0.43$	$L_{xy} = 0.00$	$L_{xz} = 0.00$
$L_{yx} = 0.00$	$L_{yy} = 1.26$	$L_{yz} = 0.00$
$L_{zx} = 0.00$	$L_{zy} = 0.00$	$L_{zz} = 1.26$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

$I_{xx} = 0.43$	$I_{xy} = 0.00$	$I_{xz} = 0.00$
$I_{yx} = 0.00$	$I_{yy} = 2809.77$	$I_{yz} = 0.00$
$I_{zx} = 0.00$	$I_{zy} = 0.00$	$I_{zz} = 2809.77$

Mass properties of Assem_S2_FUEL_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL (FUELED)

Configuration: Default

Coordinate system: -- default --

Mass (user-overridden) = 71.79 kilograms

Volume = 0.02 cubic meters

Surface area = 4.76 square meters

Center of mass: (meters)

X = 12.75

Y = 0.00

Z = 0.00

Principal axes of inertia and principal moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass.

$I_x = (1.00, 0.00, 0.00)$ $P_x = 1.79$

$I_y = (0.00, 0.71, -0.71)$ $P_y = 5.25$

$I_z = (0.00, 0.71, 0.71)$ $P_z = 5.25$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the center of mass and aligned with the output coordinate system.

$L_{xx} = 1.79$ $L_{xy} = 0.00$ $L_{xz} = 0.00$

$L_{yx} = 0.00$ $L_{yy} = 5.25$ $L_{yz} = 0.00$

$L_{zx} = 0.00$ $L_{zy} = 0.00$ $L_{zz} = 5.25$

Moments of inertia: (kilograms * square meters)

Taken at the output coordinate system.

$I_{xx} = 1.79$ $I_{xy} = 0.00$ $I_{xz} = 0.00$

$I_{yx} = 0.00$ $I_{yy} = 11666.46$ $I_{yz} = 0.00$

$I_{zx} = 0.00$ $I_{zy} = 0.00$ $I_{zz} = 11666.46$

APPENDIX

B. MATLAB® LIVE SCRIPT

LIQUID PROPULSION SYSTEM SIZING STUDY

```
#####  
%Project: Spacecraft Structures & Mechanisms Course 2019  
%Supervisor: Prof. Mario CHIARELLI  
% Author: Ahmed NOSSEIR  
#####  
format shortG
```

Preliminary Design

```
%TWRATIO = 30; %Thrust to Weight Ratio  
TWRATIO = 70; %Thrust to Weight Ratio  
g0= 9.81;  
n=1; % n-G  
F = mass_total * TWRATIO * n*g0; %Thrust (N)  
disp_F = ['Thrust (N) = ', num2str(F) ];
```

Engine Envelope Estimates

```
% Preliminary Envelope Mass [EQ 5.4 SPAD -by HUMBLE]  
m_E = F / (n*9.81* (0.0006098*F+13.44));  
disp_m_E = ['Preliminary Engine Envelope Mass m_E (kg) = ', num2str(m_E)];  
  
%Preliminary Envelope Length [EQ 5.5 SPAD -by HUMBLE]  
l_E = 0.0054*F + 31.92 ;  
disp_l_E = ['Preliminary Engine Envelope Length l_E (cm) = ', num2str(l_E)];  
  
%Preliminary Envelope Diameter [EQ 5.6 SPAD -by HUMBLE]  
d_E = 0.00357*F + 14.48 ;  
disp_d_E = ['Preliminary Engine Envelope Diameter d_E (cm) = ', num2str(d_E)];  
  
%Display  
disp(disp_F)
```

Thrust (N) = 4000.0

Thrust (N) = 85000.0

```
disp(disp_m_E)  
disp(disp_l_E)  
disp(disp_d_E)
```

```
%fuel_density = 1080 % (kg/m^3)
fuel_density = 1060 % LP Chilled(kg/m^3)
```

```
fuel_density =
    1060
```

```
oxi_density = 1140 % LOX(kg/m^3)
```

```
oxi_density =
    1140
```

```
avg_density = (fuel_density + oxi_density) / 2 % (kg/m^3)
```

```
avg_density =
    1100
```

```
#####STAGE-1#####
Isp_SC = 346 % sealevel (s)
```

```
Isp_SC =
    346
```

Step 2: Assume Inert Mass Fraction (Inert Mass / Total Mass)

value ranges from [0.005 : 0.30] average Value for Space Engines = 0.17 [SPAD book Fig.5.22]

```
#####STAGE-2#####
f_inert = 0.25
```

```
f_inert =
    0.25
```

```
#####STAGE-1#####
f_inert_SC = 0.09
```

```
f_inert_SC =
    0.09
```

Step 3: Calculate PROPELLANT MASS

[SPAD book Eq. 5.27]

```
#####STAGE-2#####%  
m_prop = (m_pay*(exp(delta_v/(Isp*g0)) - 1)*(1 - f_inert)) / (1 - f_inert *  
exp(delta_v/(Isp*g0)))  %(kg)
```

```
m_prop =  
195.59
```

```
#####STAGE-1#####%  
m_prop_SC = (m_pay_SC*(exp(delta_v_SC/(Isp_SC*g0)) - 1)*(1 - f_inert_SC)) / (1  
- f_inert_SC * exp(delta_v_SC/(Isp_SC*g0)))  %(kg)
```

```
m_prop_SC =  
5607.2
```

Step 4: Calculate Inert Mass of Engine

[SPAD book Eq 1.24]

```
#####STAGE-2#####%  
m_inert = f_inert/(1-f_inert) * m_prop  %(kg)
```

```
m_inert =  
64.78
```

```
#####SPACECRAFT#####%  
m_inert_sc = f_inert_SC/(1-f_inert_SC) * m_prop_SC  %(kg)
```

```
m_inert_sc =  
554.5
```

Step 5: Calculate Initial Mass & Final Mass of Vehicle

```
#####STAGE-2#####%  
m_initial = m_pay + m_inert + m_prop  %TOTAL WET(kg)
```

```
m_initial =  
317.80
```

$$m_{\text{final}} = m_{\text{initial}} - m_{\text{prop}} \quad \text{\% (kg)}$$

$m_{\text{final}} =$
122.21

#####STAGE-1#####

$$m_{\text{initial_SC}} = m_{\text{pay_SC}} + m_{\text{inert_sc}} + m_{\text{prop_SC}} \quad \text{\% (kg)}$$

$m_{\text{initial_SC}} =$
6192.6

$$m_{\text{final_SC}} = m_{\text{initial_SC}} - m_{\text{prop_SC}} \quad \text{\% (kg)}$$

$m_{\text{final_SC}} =$
585.4

Propellant Physical Characteristics

#####STAGE-2#####

$$m_{\text{fuel}} = m_{\text{prop}} / (1 + \text{OFRATIO}) \quad \text{\% (kg)}$$

$m_{\text{fuel}} =$
54.5

$$m_{\text{oxi}} = m_{\text{prop}} * (\text{OFRATIO} / (\text{OFRATIO} + 1)) \quad \text{\% (kg)}$$

$m_{\text{oxi}} =$
141.5

$$\text{Vol_fuel} = m_{\text{fuel}} / \text{fuel_density} \quad \text{\% (m^3)}$$

$\text{Vol_fuel} =$
0.055

APPENDIX

C. ITERATIVE DESIGN, TRADE-OFFS, & VERIFICATION

“Following are the results of iterative design procedures. The values of velocity budget in the mission analysis can be noticed to have improved in the final preliminary design provided in first chapters. Also, more accurate results for various components of the launcher have been acquired through the iterative design procedure.”

a. Mission Analysis

The required final orbit for the launch vehicle payload -the micro-satellites- will be 250km circular orbit with 38deg inclination. The launching site suggested is MARS-Wallops (37.940194°N). Thus, a final velocity, $V_{250\text{km Circular Orbit}} = 7755 \text{ m/s}$, to be considered. The second stage is supposed to cover a $\Delta V_2 = 2425 \text{ m/s}$ incase the First stage of the Launcher achieves a velocity of 5355 m/s at main engine cut-off (MECO) at time of 150s from launch. Thus, the change in velocity spent by the first stage is estimated to be $\Delta V_1 = 6550 \text{ m/s}$. Therefore, $\Delta V_{\text{Total}} = 8975 \text{ m/s}$.

b. LAUNCHER'S SECOND STAGE: PRILIMINARY DESIGN

Requirements	Quantity	Comments
ΔV	2425 (m/s)	Required for 250 circular orbit altitude raising after 108km MECO insertion point
m_{payload}	70 (kg)	Including 60kg micro-sats and 10kg design margin
Propellant	Liquid Propylene/LOX	Properties mentioned in section [I.2]
Engine Thrust	3500N	LP-2 Space Engine
Inert-mass-fraction	0.30	f_{inert}

i. MASS & ENVELOPE ESTIMATIN FOR (SPACE-ENGINE)

Engine Thrust:Weight	$\frac{F}{W}$	= 15.6 (SPAD Section 5.1)
Engine Mass	$m_E = \frac{F}{g_0 \frac{F}{W}}$	= 22.9kg
Engine Length	$L_E = 0.0054 F + 31.92$	= 50.8cm
Engine Diameter	$D_E = 0.00357 F + 14.48$	= 26.9cm

ii. PROPELLANT PROPERTIES

PROPELLANT	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	O/F	Specific Impulse $I_{sp\ vac}$ (s)
Liquid Propylene	1080 (chilled)	2.6	350
Liquid Oxygen	1140		

iii. PRESSURE-FED SYSTEM

Conventional pressure-fed system with external Helium pressurant tanks was proposed at the beginning of the study.

iv. COOLING SYSTEM

LP-1 and LP-2 engines employ two cooling techniques, primarily, Ablative Cooling System, and a secondary incorporated system which is Film Cooling. During the combustion hot gases vaporize the ablator material that lines the combustion chamber wall. These materials tend to be silica, quartz, carbon cloth and resin composites attached to the thrust chamber, as already seen on the engines used in Vector-R. as for Film Cooling (Boundary Layer Cooling), the injectors intentionally throw liquid fuel in vicinity of the chamber walls. A film of liquid propellant is formed along the chamber walls; as the cooler film flows along the walls it increases the thermal resistance and reduces the wall temperature.

v. PROPELLANT MASS ESTIMATION

$$m_{propellant} = \frac{m_{payload} [e^{\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}} - 1] (1 - f_{inert})}{1 - f_{inert} \cdot e^{\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}} = 131.07kg$$

$$m_{fuel} = \frac{m_{propellant}}{1 + O/F} = 37.4kg$$

$$m_{oxidizer} = m_{propellant} \frac{O/F}{1 + O/F} = 94.66kg$$

$$V_{fuel} = \frac{m_{fuel}}{\rho_{fuel}} \sim 0.065m^3$$

$$V_{oxidizer} = \frac{m_{ox}}{\rho_{ox}} \sim 0.095m^3$$

Approximate values are slightly greater than the actual values for design considerations.

c. LAUNCHER'S SECOND STAGE: SYSTEM SIZING, DESIGN, & TRADE-OFF

i. PROPELLANT TANKS PRESSURIZING FOR (PRESSURE-FED SYSTEMS)

$$P_{tank} = (10^{-0.1281[\log(V_{tank}) + 0.2498]}) \times 10^6$$

$$P_{\text{tank Fuel}} = 1.32 \text{ MPa}$$

$$P_{\text{tank OX}} = 1.26 \text{ MPa}$$

$$p_b = fs \cdot \text{MEOP (Burst Pressure)}$$

$$p_{b \text{ Fuel}} = 2.64 \text{ MPa}$$

$$p_{b \text{ OX}} = 2.54 \text{ MPa}$$

ii. PROPELLANT TANKS SIZING

Propellant Tanks Material	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Ultimate Tensile Strength F_{tu} (GPa)	Structure Efficiency Factor $F_{tu} / \rho \cdot g_0$ (km)	Tank Mass Factor Φ_{tank} (m)
Graphite Fibers Composite	1550	0.862	58.88	10,000

Data taken from reference [9]

For preliminary design, either cylindrical tanks with spherical ends or perfect spherical shape tanks shall be considered.

Fuel Tank (spherical)

$$V_{\text{Fuel Tank}} = 0.065 \text{ m}^3$$

$$r_s = 0.25 \text{ m}$$

Oxidizer Tank (cylindrical)

$$V_{\text{OX Tank}} = 0.095 \text{ m}^3$$

$$r_s = r_c = 0.25 \text{ m}$$

$$l_c = \frac{V_{\text{OX Tank}} - \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} = 0.15 \text{ m}$$

Tank Masses are estimated using pV/W approach

$$\Phi_{\text{tank}} = \frac{p_b \cdot V}{m_{\text{tank}} \cdot g_0}$$

$$m_{\text{tank Fuel}} \cong 2.0 \text{ kg}$$

$$m_{\text{tank OX}} \cong 2.5 \text{ kg}$$

iii. PRESURRANT SYSTEM

Considering (Helium) as pressurant gas with characteristics;

Isentropic Parameter (specific heats ration)	γ	= 1.66
He Gas constant	$R = \frac{R_u}{\mu}$	= 8314/4.003
Molecular mass of He	μ	= 4.003 kg/kmol

$P_i = 21.0 \text{ MPa}$ Typical Lowest Value for initial pressure.

$P_f = 1.30 \text{ MPa}$ Mean value of the propellant tanks pressure.

For long thrust duration we assume isentropic change in temperature, since there is no sufficient time for heat transfer between pressurant and propellant.

$$T_f = T_i \left(\frac{P_f}{P_i} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}}$$

$$m_{press} = \frac{V_{press} P_f}{R T_f}$$

$$V_{press} = V_{tanks \text{ prop}} + V_{tanks \text{ press}}$$

$$V_{press @ T_i P_i} = \frac{m_{press} R T_i}{P_i}$$

Firstly, $V_{tanks \text{ press}}$ is assumed to be Zero, as the value is unknown. Then iterations should be made, after calculating mass of pressurant with the value of only propellant tanks volume (adding a 5% design margin to the $V_{tanks \text{ prop}}$), in order to know the correct value for V_{press} . Volume of pressurant inside pressurant tank is then calculated at T_i & P_i (273K & 21.0MPa). The final sizing estimate values are;

$$m_{press} = 1.1 \text{ kg}$$

$$V_{tanks \text{ press}} = 0.03 \text{ m}^3$$

Mass of Pressurant tank is estimated using the pV/W approach; Noting that 3 tanks shall be used of Titanium material with Tank-Mass-Factor $\phi_{tank} = 6350 \text{ m}$.

$$m_{tank \text{ He}} = \frac{21 \times 10^6 * 0.01}{9.81 * 6350} = 3.4 \text{ kg per tank}$$

If three cylindrical tanks with spherical ends are used with $r_s = r_c = 0.1 \text{ m}$ each, then the cylinder lengths is calculated to be;

$$l_c = \frac{V_{tank \text{ press}} - \frac{4}{3} \pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} = 0.185 \text{ m}$$

Therefore, the Overall-length and outer diameter will be;

$$OAL = 38.5 \text{ cm}$$

$$\phi_{out} = 20 \text{ cm}$$

iv. MASSES OF THRUST VECTOR CONTROL (TVC), & FEED SYSTEM

Included in $m_E = 22.9 \text{ kg}$

v. STRUCTURAL MOUNTS MASSES

Represents about 5-10% from main components masses. Calculated through;

$$0.1(m_E + m_{Propellant \text{ Tanks}} + m_{Press. \text{ Tank}}) \approx 4 \text{ kg}$$

d. LAUNCHER'S FIRST STAGE: PRILIMINARY DESIGN

Requirements	Quantity	Comments
ΔV	6550 (m/s)	Required for 108km MECO insertion point at t=150s
$m_{payload}$	300 (kg)	Including 280kg for Stage-2 (+margin) and 20kg design margin for Stage-1 payload.
Propellant	Liquid Propylene/LOX	Properties mentioned in section [2.2.2]
Engine Thrust	25,000N	(x3) LP-1 Sea Level Engine
Inert-mass-fraction	0.10	f_{inert}

i. MASS & ENVELOPE ESTIMATIN FOR (SPACE-ENGINE)

Engine Thrust:Weight	$\frac{F}{W}$	= 70
Engine Mass (three LP-1 Engines are used)	$m_E = \frac{F}{g_0 \frac{F}{W}}$	= 36.4kg (per Engine)
Engine Length	$L_E = 0.0054 F + 31.92$	= 32.8cm
Engine Diameter	$D_E = 0.00357 F + 14.48$	= 18.2cm

ii. PROPELLANT PROPERTIES

PROPELLANT	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	O/F	Specific Impulse I_{sp} sea level (s)
Liquid Propylene	1080 (chilled)	2.6	347
Liquid Oxygen	1140		

iii. PRESSURE-FED SYSTEM

Similar to section 2.2.3.

iv. ABLATIVE COOLING SYSTEM

Similar to section 2.2.4

v. PROPELLANT MASS ESTIMATION

The Ideal Rocket Equation will be used directly in its classic form, knowing that VECTOR-R Launcher lift-off mass is supposed to be ~6000kg.

$$\frac{m_i}{m_i - m_{prop}} = \exp^{\frac{\Delta V}{I_{sp} \cdot g_0}}$$

Given that, $m_i = 6100kg$
 $\Delta V = 6550 m/s$
 $I_{sp} = 347s$
 Thus; $m_{prop} = 5209.5$

$$m_{inert} = m_i - m_{payload} - m_{prop}$$

Therefore, $m_{inert} = 590.5kg$ which justifies that, $f_{inert} = 0.098 \approx 10\%$.

$$m_{fuel} = \frac{m_{propellant}}{1 + \frac{O}{F}} = 1447.0kg$$

$$m_{oxidizer} = m_{propellant} \frac{O/F}{1 + O/F} = 3762.5kg$$

$$V_{fuel} = \frac{m_{fuel}}{\rho_{fuel}} = 1.34m^3$$

$$V_{oxidizer} = \frac{m_{ox}}{\rho_{ox}} = 3.3m^3$$

e. LAUNCHER'S FIRST STAGE: SYSTEM SIZING, DESIGN, & TRADE-OFF

i. PROPELLANT TANKS PRESSURIZING FOR (PRESSURE-FED SYSTEMS)

$$P_{tank} = (10^{-0.1281[\log(V_{tank}) + 0.2498]}) \times 10^6$$

$$P_{tank Fuel} = 0.895MPa$$

$$P_{tank ox} = 0.797MPa$$

$$p_b = fs \cdot MEOP \text{ (Burst Pressure)}$$

$$p_b Fuel = 1.79MPa$$

$$p_b ox = 1.594MPa$$

ii. PROPELLANT TANKS SIZING

Propellant Tanks Material	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Ultimate Tensile Strength F_{tu} (GPa)	Structure Efficiency Factor $F_{tu} / \rho \cdot g_0$ (km)	Tank Mass Factor Φ_{tank} (m)
Graphite Fibers Composite	1550	0.862	58.88	10,000

For preliminary design of propellant tanks in Stage-1, cylindrical tanks with spherical ends shall be considered.

Fuel Tank	Oxidizer Tank
$V_{Fuel\ Tank} = 1.34m^3$	$V_{OX\ Tank} = 3.3m^3$
$r_s = r_c = 0.5m$	
$l_c = \frac{V_{Fuel\ Tank} - \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} = 1.04m$	$l_c = \frac{V_{OX\ Tank} - \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} = 3.53m$

Tank Masses are estimated using pV/W approach

$$\phi_{tank} = \frac{p_b \cdot V}{m_{tank} \cdot g_0}$$

$$m_{tank\ Fuel} \cong 24.5kg$$

$$m_{tank\ Ox} \cong 53.6kg$$

iii. PRESURRANT SYSTEM

Similar to Stage-2 calculations, considering (Helium) as pressurant gas with characteristics;

Isentropic Parameter (specific heats ration)	γ	= 1.66
He Gas constant	$R = \frac{R_u}{\mu}$	= 8314/4.003
Molecular mass of He	μ	= 4.003 kg/kmol

$P_i = 21.0\ MPa$ Typical Lowest Value for initial pressure.

$P_f = 0.846\ MPa$ Mean value of the propellant tanks pressure.

For long thrust duration we assume Isentropic change in temperature, since there is insufficient time for heat transfer between pressurant and propellant.

$$T_f = T_i \left(\frac{P_f}{P_i} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}}$$

$$m_{press} = \frac{V_{press} P_f}{R T_f}$$

$$V_{press} = V_{tanks\ prop} + V_{tanks\ press}$$

$$V_{press\ @\ T_i\ P_i} = \frac{m_{press} R T_i}{P_i}$$

Firstly, $V_{tanks\ press}$ is assumed to be Zero, as the value is unknown. Then iterations should be made, after calculating mass of pressurant with the value of only propellant tanks volume (adding a 5% design margin to the $V_{tanks\ prop}$), in order to know the correct value for V_{press} . Volume of pressurant inside pressurant tank is then calculated at T_i & P_i (273K & 21.0MPa). The final sizing estimate values are;

$$m_{press} = 30kg$$

$$V_{tank\ press.} = 0.81m^3$$

Mass of Pressurant tank is estimated using the pV/W approach; Noting that only one tank shall be used of Titanium material with Tank-Mass-Factor $\phi_{tank} = 6350m$.

$$m_{tank\ He} = \frac{21 \times 10^6 * 0.81}{9.81 * 6350} = 273kg$$

If a cylindrical tank with spherical ends is used with $r_s = r_c = 0.4m$ then the cylinder length is calculated to be;

$$l_c = \frac{V_{tank\ press} - \frac{4}{3}\pi r_s^3}{\pi r_c^2} = 1.0m$$

Therefore, the Overall-length and outer diameter will be;

$$OAL = 1.8m$$

$$\phi_{out} = 0.8m$$

iv. MASSES OF THRUST VECTOR CONTROL (TVC), & FEED SYSTEM

Included in $m_E = 36.4kg$

v. STRUCTURAL MOUNTS MASSES

Represents about 5-10% from main components masses. Calculated through;

$$0.1(m_E + m_{Propellant\ Tanks} + m_{Press.\ Tank}) \approx 40kg$$

f. MASS BUDGET SUMMARY for VECTOR-R Launcher

SECOND STAGE

Component	Mass (kg)	Comments
Liquid Propylene	37.0	
Liquid Oxygen	95.0	
He Pressurant	1.10	
Engine + TVC + FEED-SYSTEM	23.0	
Fuel Tank	2.0	
LOX Tank	2.5	
Pressurant Tank	10.5	
Structural Mounts	4	
Payload	70	
Total Wet	244.6	
Total Dry	41.5	Excluding propellant & payload
m_{inert} estimated	56.5	For $f_{inert} = 0.30$
Mass expected for structure $\sim 15kg$.. putting in consideration that a margin of 20kg can be utilized.		

*Despite the Total Wet and Structural Mass together to be $\cong 260kg$, the **total weight assumed for Second Stage will be 280kg** with design margin, to be considered in First Stage Preliminary Design.

FIRST STAGE

Component	Mass (kg)	Comments
Liquid Propylene	1447.0	$m_{prop} = 5209.5kg$
Liquid Oxygen	3762.5	
He Pressurant	30.0	
Engine + TVC + FEED-SYSTEM	120	For the three "LP-1" Engines with 10kg margin.
Fuel Tank	24.0	
LOX Tank	54.0	
Pressurant Tank	273.0	
Structural Mounts	40.0	
Payload	300	Stage-2=260kg, +20kg margin for Stage-2, +20kg margin for Stage-1 design.
Total Wet	6050.5	
Total Dry	511	Excluding propellant & payload
m_{inert} estimated	590.5	$m_{inert} = 6100 - 300 - 5209.5$
Mass expected for structure $\sim 80kg$.. putting in consideration that a margin of 20kg can be utilized.		

APPENDIX

D. FLIGHT SIMULATOR

Vehicle Overview and Simulation Results can be accessed through this link:

<https://www2.flightclub.io/result/2d?id=f1a34014-b194-47de-b10f-6e02d48f12f5>

The following figure shows the *Vehicle Overview*. Stages are defined as VECTOR-R – Stage 1 & Stage – 2. Each stage has its name and number of engines listed with the mass properties included with design margins. ΔV estimates mentioned here is calculated by the simulator according to the input parameters in Stage Properties and Engine Properties assigned by the user. The estimate made by the simulator for ΔV Total Vehicle is 9.39 km/s. This was found almost similar to $\Delta V_{total} = 9500 \frac{m}{s}$ (from Section 2.1 Mission Analysis) which is set as design parameter after convergence during the launcher design iterative process. It is worthy to mention that in the early design iterations ΔV_{Total} was set to be 8975 m/s (see Appendix C section a. Mission Analysis).

First-Stage Engine LP-1 and Second-Stage Engines LP-2 (LP: Liquid Propylene). Specific Impulse values are averaged in Chapter 2 calculations and are specified with lower bound and upper bound in the Flight Simulator Engine Properties.

← Engine Properties 📄

Engine template ▾

# of engines	Name				
3	LP-1				
Sea Level Isp (s)	Vacuum Isp (s)	Sea Level Thrust (N)	Vacuum Thrust (N)	Mass (kg)	Throttle Capability
340	350	28500	35000	35	0.47
Seconds to Full Thrust					
6					

← Engine Properties 📄

Engine template ▾

# of engines	Name				
1	LP-2				
Sea Level Isp (s)	Vacuum Isp (s)	Sea Level Thrust (N)	Vacuum Thrust (N)	Mass (kg)	Throttle Capability
0	350	0	4000	0	0.4
Seconds to Full Thrust					
6					

← Stage Properties

Stage template ▾

Name

VECTOR-R - Stage 1

Radius (m)

1.2

Length (m)

9.15

Dry Mass (kg)

555

Fuel Capacity (kg)

1558

Propellant Mass (kg)

5608

Minimum Fuel Limit (kg)

10

Max Acceleration (g's)

8

Fairing Radius (m)

Fairing Mass (kg)

← Stage Properties

Stage template ▾

Name

VECTOR-R - Stage 2

Radius (m)

0.7

Length (m)

3

Dry Mass (kg)

65

Fuel Capacity (kg)

70

Propellant Mass (kg)

200

Minimum Fuel Limit (kg)

4

Max Acceleration (g's)

6

Fairing Radius (m)

0.7

Fairing Mass (kg)

10

Launch Site Data:

MARS – WALLOPS
Mid-Atlantic Regional Spaceport

← Custom Launchpad

Description
Mid-Atlantic Regional Spaceport

Latitude
37.8339798

Longitude
-75.4877202

Elevation
0

Launch Events:

Events	
T+1.0	Main Engine Ignition
T+4.7	Launch
T+216.0	MECO-1
T+225.0	Second Stage Ignition
T+251.0	Payload Fairing Jettison
T+427.0	SECO-1
T+546.0	Microsatellites Separation
T1368.799999993017	Fuel Depletion

Flight Profile:

Main Engine Ignition Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Throttle-5 Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Throttle-3 Stage 2 - VECTOR-R
Throttle-1 Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Stage 1 Guidance Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	SECO-1 Stage 2 - VECTOR-R
Launch Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Stage 1 Guidance Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Microsatellites Separation Stage 2 - VECTOR-R
Pitch Kick Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	MECO-1 Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	
Stage 1 Guidance Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	First Stage Separation Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	
Throttle Down to 55% Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Guidance-0 Stage 2 - VECTOR-R	
Stage 1 Guidance Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Payload Fairing Jettison Stage 2 - VECTOR-R	
Throttle Up to 100% Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Second Stage Ignition Stage 2 - VECTOR-R	
Stage 1 Guidance Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Stage 2 Guidance Stage 2 - VECTOR-R	
Stage 1 Guidance Stage 1 - VECTOR-R	Throttle-1 Stage 2 - VECTOR-R	

APPENDIX

E. TECHNICAL DRAWINGS

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
 DIMENSIONS ARE IN **METERS**
 SURFACE FINISH:
 TOLERANCES:
 LINEAR:
 ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
 BREAK SHARP
 EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

CENTER OF MASSES

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

TITLE:

LAUNCHER
 FUELED

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

ASSEMBLY_FULL_LAUNCHER_FUELED

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:200

SHEET 1 OF 1

Ø 1000.00

DETAIL A
SCALE 1 : 5

5400.00mm

SCALE 1:25

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

First-Stage LOX Tank Unibody Structure

Materials
Tank: Filament-Wound Hexcel Carbon-Epoxy.
Inner Tube: +-45deg Carbon-Epoxy.
Longt.Stiffeners: UD Carbon-Epoxy.
Over-wrap: Aramid(Kevlar49)-Epoxy.

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN	AHMED NOSSER		
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

Full_Assem_S1_LOX_Tank

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:50

SHEET 1 OF 1

DETAIL A
SCALE 1 : 5

SCALE 1:20

SCALE 1:15

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:	FINISH:	DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES	DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	REVISION

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

TITLE:	
MATERIAL:	
DWG NO.	
WEIGHT:	
SCALE: 1:50	
SHEET 1 OF 1	

Full_Assem_S1_Fuel_Tank

A4

SCALE 1:8

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

SECOND-STAGE UNIBODY LOX TANK

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHK'D			
APP'V'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

TITLE:			
MATERIAL:			
DWG NO.			
Assem_S2_LOX_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL		A4	
WEIGHT:			
SCALE: 1:20	SHEET 1 OF 1		

SCALE 1:8

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

SECOND-STAGE UNIBODY FUEL TANK

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

TITLE:

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

SCALE:1:10

SHEET 1 OF 1

Assem_S2_FUEL_TANK_UNIBODY_FULL

A4

DETAIL A
SCALE 1 : 5

SCALE 1:20

SCALE 1:15

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

Assem_InnerTube_and_Strips

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

Materials:

Strips (Longt. Stringers):
carbon-epoxy composite +30deg
Inner tube:
carbon-epoxy composite +45deg

MATERIAL:

Structure used in Unibody S-1 Fuel Tank

DWG NO.

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:50

SHEET 1 OF 1

SCALE 1:25

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:	FINISH:	DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES	DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	REVISION

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE	
DRAWN				
CHK'D				
APPV'D				
MFG				
Q.A				

TITLE:	
MATERIAL:	
DWG NO.	
WEIGHT:	
SCALE: 1:50	SHEET 1 OF 1

Assem_LOX_InnerTube_and_Str

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
 DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
 SURFACE FINISH:
 TOLERANCES:
 LINEAR:
 ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
 BREAK SHARP
 EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

First-Stage LOX TANK

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

MATERIALS:
 Tank:
 Filament-wound Hexcel Carbon-epoxy
 Tank Caps:
 Titanium commercial alloy

MATERIAL:
 DWG NO. **Assem_LOX_Tank_Ti_Caps** A4

WEIGHT: SCALE: 1:50 SHEET 1 OF 1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:			FINISH:	DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES	DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	REVISION
DRAWN			SIGNATURE	DATE	Materials: Tube: Carbon-Epoxy Composite +-45deg Stringers: Carbon-Epoxy Composite +-30deg	
CHK'D					DWG NO.	
APPV'D					A4	
MFG			MATERIAL:		Assem_S2_FUEL_TANK_LONGT.STRINGERS_INNER_TUBE	
Q.A			WEIGHT:		SCALE:1:10	
					SHEET 1 OF 1	

SCALE 1:5

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:			FINISH:	DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES	DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	REVISION
					Second-Stage Fuel Tank	
DRAWN	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE		Materials: Tank: Filament-wound Carbon-Epoxy Tank Caps- Titanium Alloy	
CHK'D						
APPV'D						
MFG						
Q.A				MATERIAL:	DWG NO.	A4
				Assem_S2_FUEL_TANK_Ti_CAPS		
				WEIGHT:	SCALE:1:10	SHEET 1 OF 1

DETAIL A
SCALE 1:2

SCALE 1:8

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN		
CHK'D		
APPV'D		
MFG		
Q.A		

TITLE:	
MATERIAL:	
DWG NO.	
SCALE: 1:20	SHEET 1 OF 1

Assem_S2_LOX_TANK_LONGT.STRINGERS

SCALE 1:8

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

SECOND-STAGE LOX TANK

Materials:

Tank: Filament-wound Hexcel
Carbon-Epoxy composite
Tank Caps: Titanium Alloys

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

Assem_S2_LOX_TANK_Ti_CAPS A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:20

SHEET 1 OF 1

SCALE 1:20

SCALE 1:15

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

Assem_Tank_Ti_Caps

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE	
DRAWN				
CHK'D				
APPV'D				
MFG				
Q.A				

Materials

Caps: Titanium Alloy
Tank: Carbon-epoxy composite

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

First-Stage Fuel Tank

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:50

SHEET 1 OF 1

SCALE 1:1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

SECOND-STAGE AIRFRAME
LONGITUDINAL FURRING BEAM

Material:

Carbon-epoxy composite +-30deg

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

S2_FURRING_BEAM

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:20

SHEET 1 OF 1

730.00mm

40.00

SCALE 1:1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

Second-Stage Unibody-Fuel Tank Longt. Stringer

Materials:

CarbonFiber-Epoxy Composite

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN			
CHKD			
APPVD			
MFG			
Q.A			

MATERIAL:

S2_LONGT_STRINGER_T_60x40x3x3mm

DWG NO.

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:5

SHEET 1 OF 1

SECTION A-A
SCALE 1 : 10

SCALE 1:10

SCALE 1:4

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN **MILLIMETERS**
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN	AHMED NOSSEIR		
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

Material:

Additive Manufacturing
Carbon Composite

DWG NO.

S2_FRAME

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:20

SHEET 1 OF 1

SECTION A-A
SCALE 1 : 10

SCALE 1:10

SCALE 1:4

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED:
DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS
SURFACE FINISH:
TOLERANCES:
LINEAR:
ANGULAR:

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN	AHMED NOSSEIR		
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

Material:
**Additive Manufacturing
Carbon Composite**

DWG NO.
S2_INTERMEDIATE_PANEL

A4

WEIGHT:

SCALE:1:20

SHEET 1 OF 1

SECTION A-A
SCALE 1 : 10

SCALE 1:10

SCALE 1:4

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS		FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
SURFACE FINISH:									
TOLERANCES:									
LINEAR:									
ANGULAR:									
NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		Material:			
DRAWN AHMED NOSSEIR						Additive Manufacturing			
CHK'D						Carbon Composites			
APPV'D									
MFG									
Q.A									
						DWG NO.			
						S2_TOP_OR_BOTTOM_PANEL		A4	
						SCALE:1:20		SHEET 1 OF 1	

DETAIL A
SCALE 2 : 15

DETAIL B
SCALE 2 : 15

DETAIL C
SCALE 2 : 15

SCALE 1:15

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS			FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
SURFACE FINISH:										
TOLERANCES:										
LINEAR:										
ANGULAR:										
DRAWN		NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		TITLE:		
CHK'D		AHMED NOSSEIR						Second-Stage Airframe with Unibody Propellant Tanks		
APPV'D								DWG NO.		
MFG								Assem_S2_AIRFRAME		
Q.A								A3		
						MATERIAL:		SCALE:1:20		
						WEIGHT:		SHEET 1 OF 1		